

ARIES

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Technical report on Work Packages completed at M48 and summary of Transnational Access at M48

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ABSTRACT

The Amendment to the Grant Agreement approved in December 2020 to mitigate the impact of the Covid crisis has remodulated the ARIES Workplan, extending some Work Packages by up to 12 months while others have maintained their original termination date. The Work Packages with no or limited extension are Work Packages 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 15 that were completed in April 2021, and Work Package 14 completed in August 2021.

This deliverable report is intended to present and disseminate the final results of the Work Packages terminated between April and August 2021, in anticipation of the Final Report that is expected only in June 2022. For each Work Package, are presented the work carried out during the 4th year of the project (M37-M48), the context and objectives for the entire project, and the main scientific and technical results. A final section underlines their potential impact on accelerator science and technology. A compilation of publications and exploitable foreground completes this part of the report.

The second part of the report summarises the status of ARIES Transnational Access (TA) activities at M48 (April 2021). All ARIES TA's have been extended by one year to compensate for the Covid-related delays and to redistribute access between more and less successful facilities.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

The ARIES Work Packages 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 (Network Activities), and 14, 15 (Joint Research Activities) have been completed between April and August 2021. Presented here are a summary of their activities during the last period the project (from April 2020 to termination),, their context and objectives for the entire project, and the main scientific and technical results achieved during the entire project. A final chapter underlines their potential impact on accelerator science and technology, followed by a compilation of their publications and exploitable foreground.

The second part of the report presents the status of ARIES Transnational Access (TA) activities at M48 (April 2021), in terms of projects, users, and access units after Year 4 and since the start of the projects. The TA indicators are compared to the target values from the Grant Agreement. It appears that the Covid-related restrictions to travel in spring 2021 have again impacted some facilities that have provided only limited access, while other facilities have been less impacted and have been able to provide more access than required. On average, the access provided by the project is in line with the objectives, but large disparities between facilities are present.

1. Work carried out during the 3rd reporting period (M37-M48)

1.2 WP3 INDUSTRIAL AND SOCIETAL APPLICATIONS

1.2.1 Task 3.2. Low energy electron beam applications: new technology development

Guidelines for the construction of radiation installation for ballast water treatment using electron beam

The INCT has made a study of the use of electron beams for treating ballast water from ships and a report on this activity has been written. The report presents guidelines for the construction of a radiation ballast module for ballast water. It includes the state-of-the-art in the use of radiation technique for wastewater decontamination, a description of the technological process of radiation treatment of ballast water, determination of the process efficiency of ballast water radiation treatment, discussion on the choice of the accelerator and the technology of sludge irradiation, the definition of guidelines for the accelerator and biological shields installation, and discussion of radiation protection issues.

Virus inactivation for vaccine production

During the third period the main activity of FEP was the technology development for inactivation biohazards using very-low energy electron irradiation, below 300 keV (Fig. 1). Together with two other Fraunhofer partners the goal was an efficient and environmentally safe inactivation of different viruses for vaccine production. Based on the long-term experience in laboratory scale inactivation by electrons the development focused on an industrial usable process, designed for Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) production and able to handle a remarkable throughput of some liters per hour of virus suspensions.

The successful results show a very good virus inactivation for many virus types with much better antigen recovery than at alternative technologies, like chemical inactivation within a much shorter treatment time of seconds instead of days with chemical processing.

This technology could be developed up to a demonstration level and finally licensed to a first industrial equipment supplier. The technology development for other types of biohazards is ongoing.

Finally, the research group was awarded for their outstanding scientific achievements the Fraunhofer Prize for “Human- and Environment-Centered Technology” 2021.

Fig. 1: 300 keV irradiation equipment for virus suspension (left), flow scheme for safe handling of biohazardous liquids for electron irradiation.

1.2.2 Task 3.3. Low energy electron beam applications: new applications

Radiation processing of the polymers

The INCT has prepared a report on recent developments in the radiation processing of polymers. This report presents two examples of polymer modification by EB irradiation. The first part of the work involves surface modification of selected polymers by radiation-induced grafting, while the second part includes radiation-induced modification of degradable copolymers based on aliphatic polyester.

Related to this, studies of the removal of microplastics from sewage sludge has been made by HUD, using an electron beam at the INCT. This has analysed the effect of the electron beams and demonstrated that the sedimentation of many types of microplastics is increased, potentially providing a method for removal.

1.2.3 Task 3.4. Medium energy electron beams

During the third period, the main activity of Task 3.4 has been the organization of a workshop dedicated to explore the possibility of using Very High Energy Electrons (VHEE) in Radiotherapy (RT). The workshop took place virtually on the 5-7 October 2020 and was co-organized by CERN and WP3 ARIES. More than 400 scientists from the most diverse extractions gathered virtually to evaluate and discuss the perspectives of this novel technique. This workshop followed up a similar one organized in 2017 in Daresbury [<https://www.cockcroft.ac.uk/events/VHEE17/>] and the large increase in attendance shows the vitality and increasing interest in the field. The workshop included also a very lively session dedicated to industrial partners. The list of topics explored was:

- State of the Art;
- Mechanism and Innovation for FLASH Radiation Therapy;
- New indications and hot topics;
- Facilities description: current and planned, e.g. exploitation and use of the existing facilities CLEAR, CLARA, ELBE, PITZ;

- Demonstrate capability of conventional RF acceleration techniques including SC for VHEE RT applications;
- Overall VHEE compact machine design including costing;
- Dosimetry and Detectors;
- Treatment Planning, Modelling and Imaging;
- Accelerators R&D and Technologies for medical treatment, e.g. novel acceleration techniques;
- Industrial panel for medical technologies and plans;
- Where are we going? Which experiments/facilities are needed?

Complete information about this could be found in the web page of the workshop: [<https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/>].

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P3 reporting period, Task 3.4 had one deliverable and this was achieved:

- D3.4: Design of a compact 140 MeV electron linear accelerator

1.2.4 Task 3.5. Radioisotope production

During this third period, different activities have been carried out to address the main challenges present in the current accelerators for radioisotope production. Focused on AMIT cyclotron, an extremely compact machine for PET radioisotope production, two critical issues have been studied: beam dynamics and efficient cooling systems. Concerning beam dynamics, the impact of the beam stripping has been analysed. This is of vital importance for the internal ion sources, typically used in compact cyclotrons. The residual gas injected in the acceleration region through the ion source slits leads to a degradation of the vacuum conditions, producing beam-gas residual stripping interactions which will decrease the final beam current and consequently the radioisotope production as well increase the radiation levels in the machine due to beam losses. To understand such effect, an implementation of the physical phenomena in OPAL beam dynamics code has been performed. Furthermore, the electromagnetic stripping, important for high magnetic fields, has been also integrated in the models. Both features allow the optimization of machine parameters according to the beam operation requirements. For instance, it has allowed the optimization of the ion source extraction slit as a trade-off between the injected beam for acceleration and the losses by stripping, resulting in a higher radioisotope production rate.

On the other hand, following the activities performed in the second ARIES period, the optimization of the autonomous cooling system of the AMIT cyclotron have been completed with the modification of the current leads and transfer line. It has been obtained a notable reduction of the cooling down and warm up time of the cyclotron, with the consequent benefit in the running costs and machine availability.

1.3 WP4 EFFICIENT ENERGY MANAGEMENT

1.3.1 Task 4.2 High Efficiency RF Power Sources

Studies on designing an efficient klystron at 12 GHz with 30 MW peak power have been completed, resulting in a deliverable report. The outcome of the study has been an optimized design for a 12GHz klystron that could be used for a compact light source (Fig. 2). The design includes an interaction line for optimized bunching, a double gap output cavity for maximized power coupling, and respects the surface field limit of 100MV/m. The resulting theoretical efficiency is 65.5%, calculated with realistic simulations and boundary conditions.

Fig. 2: schematic design and field simulations (top) and main parameters (bottom) of the 12 GHz klystron

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P3 reporting period, Task 4.2 had one deliverable and this was achieved:

- D4.2 - Design of an efficient klystron (M41)

1.3.2 Task 4.3. Increasing energy efficiency of the spallation target station

The simulation work on the system behaviour of the cryogenic D₂ moderator of the PSI neutron spallation source had become significantly more complex after it became obvious that the co-existence of gas- and liquid phase have to be fully included in the simulation. However, finally it was possible to finish the extended simulations and to explain the observed behaviour. Concept proposals for an improved moderator geometry could be made. Figure 3 reports the simulated neutron yield predicted gain, 1.25 to 1.31 at medium wavelength.

Fig. 3: Simulated neutron current and gain in the moderator without re-entrant cavity. 2 Å correspond to 25 meV

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P3 reporting period, Task 4.2 had one deliverable and this was achieved:

- D4.4 - Report on the optimization procedure and technical layout of efficient moderator assemblies (M46)

1.3.3 Task 4.4. High Efficiency SRF power conversion

The team has further refined the results presented in D4.1. The outcome of the study has been the design and verification of magnetic shielding for a test setup and the development of an instrument called “flux lens” for quick and reproducible measurements of the flux expulsion efficiency of Niobium sheet material. The experimental set-up using this device realised in P3 is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Experimental set-up to measure flux expulsion during cool-down.

1.3.4 Task 4.5. Efficient operation of pulsed magnets

This Task succeeded in organizing unfortunately only in remote mode the Workshop “Energy Efficient Beam Transport Technologies” (26 April 2021, <https://indico.gsi.de/event/11642/overview>) with a focus on energy efficient pulsed magnets and pulse forming circuits with energy recovery that had been delayed several times because of the Covid emergency. At the Workshop, has been presented and discussed the final achievement of the study on Pulsed Magnets for beam Transfer Channels realised in the frame of ARIES WP4 and subject of the Deliverable D4.3.

The study has carried on the simulation and optimization of a pulse forming network to minimize ohmic losses and maximize energy recovery for next pulse in pulsing a quadrupole magnet. In the final tests, 28% energy recovery was achieved, with energy efficiency improved by as much as 80%.

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P3 reporting period, Task 4.2 had one milestone and one deliverable that were achieved:

- D4.3 - Report on pulsed magnets (M43)
- MS21 - Workshop on efficient magnets/beam transport (M37)

1.4 WP5 EUROPEAN NETWORK FOR NOVEL ACCELERATORS

The WP5 has continued in the 3rd reporting period its work on European Network for Novel Accelerators (EuroNNAc) and on European strategies for plasma accelerators and dielectric accelerators. In particular various activities on publication, strategy discussions and an application to the ESFRI roadmap update in 2021 were pursued and involved a large number of the network partners.

Publication of EAAC 2019 Proceedings

The European Advanced Accelerator Concepts workshop (EAAC 2019) had been organized from 15 to 21 September 2019 with a record-breaking attendance of 276 registered participants, limited by the conference site capacity. The proceedings of the EAAC 2019 were prepared following a peer-review process during the 3rd reporting period and were published as Volume 1596 (2020) of the IOP conference proceedings, acknowledging EU/ARIES support and in open access format¹.

Strategy Discussions and Formation of Expert Panel “High gradient acceleration: Plasma and Laser”

In the 3rd reporting period a European Expert Panel with a strong contribution from ARIES WP5 was created and started. The 2020 Update for the European Strategy for Particle Physics emphasizes in particular the importance of innovation in accelerator technology, listing it as “a powerful driver for many accelerator-based fields of science and industry” with “technologies under consideration includ[ing] high-field magnets, high-temperature superconductors, plasma wakefield acceleration

¹ “Proceedings of the 4th European Advanced Accelerator Concepts Workshop 15-20 September 2019, Isola d'Elba, Italy. Edited by A. Cianchi et al. IOP Volume 1596 (2020).”

and other high-gradient accelerating structures” and emphasizing the need to define “deliverables for this decade [...] in a timely fashion”².

In January 2021 an expert panel “High gradient acceleration: Plasma and Laser” was initiated by the Laboratory Director’s Group (LDG) after consultation with the leadership of ARIES WP5 that had a long experience in launching and coordinating initiatives on plasma and dielectric accelerators and had already prepared a strategy to boost this research. The expert panel exhibits large overlap with WP5/EuroNNAc such that full synergy is ensured. Panel members include: Ralph Assmann (DESY/INFN, chair), Edda Gschwendtner (CERN, deputy chair), Kevin Cassou (IN2P3/IJCLab), Sebastian Corde (IP Paris), Laura Corner (Liverpool), Brigitte Cros (LPGP-CNRS-U Paris Saclay), Massimo Ferrario (INFN), Simon Hooker (Oxford), Rasmus Ischebeck (PSI), Andrea Latina (CERN), Olle Lundh (Lund), Patric Muggli (MPI Munich), Phi Nghiem (CEA/IRFU), Jens Osterhoff (DESY), Tor Raubenheimer (SLAC), Arnd Specka (IN2P3/LLR), Jorge Viera (IST), Matthew Wing (UCL). The panel is charged to develop a roadmap proposal for our domain, relevant for Particle Physics in Europe. The expert panel reports to the LDG which will discuss the proposed accelerator R&D roadmap with the CERN council.

The formation of the expert panel “High gradient acceleration: Plasma and Laser” is a further success for the field of advanced accelerators, a recognition of the scientific results achieved, and the efforts spent to disseminate those results into the accelerator field. EuroNNAc and EAAC played an important role in this process since we started them in 2012 and 2013 with its several reports on future strategy and R&D directions.

The CDR for EuPRAXIA and its Placement of the ESFRI Roadmap Update 2021

During the 3rd reporting period ARIES WP5 supported strongly the preparation of the ESFRI application of the EuPRAXIA project, the “European Plasma research Accelerator with eXcellence In Applications”. The common initiative was grown out of WP5 network discussions and continued to use EuroNNAc and the EAAC as a discussion forum. Support from WP5 included outreach activities through the network partners and contacts to European governments that supported the ESFRI application. As announced on 30 June, the ESFRI committee has selected EuPRAXIA as one of 11 future research infrastructures with highest importance for Europe. Quoting from the ESFRI press release: “There is a **new level of ambition** to develop globally unique, complex facilities for frontier science: Einstein Telescope – highest value project ever on the Roadmap - EUR 1.900 million, and EuPRAXIA – innovative accelerator based on plasma technology - EUR 569 million.” This success illustrates the impact of WP5 coordination and outreach³.

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P3 reporting period, WP5 had one deliverable and this was achieved:

- D5.2 - Final EuroNNAc and EAAC Report (M46).

² European Strategy Group, “2020 Update of the European Strategy for Particle Physics”, CERN-ESU-013.

³ Press Release ESFRI, 30 June 2021. <https://www.esfri.eu/latest-esfri-news/new-ris-roadmap-2021>

1.5 WP6 ACCELERATOR PERFORMANCE AND CONCEPTS

During the 3rd period, WP6 APEC organized two virtual workshops, which were attended by 118 and 115 participants, respectively.

The ARIES workshop on Mitigation Approaches for Hadron Storage Rings and Synchrotrons (Mitigations2020) took place from 22 June to 1 July 2020 (6 half days). It concluded with a community ranking of mitigations for space-charge effects, reviewing the situations at the CERN PSB in Switzerland, GSI UNILAC and SIS18 in Germany, at CSNS in China, at BNL RHIC, EIC, FNAL PIP-II in the US and J-PARC Main Ring in Japan. Popular mitigation measures included a reduction of the peak intensity (CERN PSB, JPARC), resonance compensation, optimization of lattice and working point (J-PARC, CERN), and, for the future, future electron lenses (CERN, GSI). The results of this workshop and of the earlier APEC2018 workshop entered in the ARIES Milestone MS31 “Identification and Prioritization of Mitigation Approaches” for Task 6.2.

The ARIES workshop on Storage Rings and Gravitational Waves (SRGW2021), held from 2 February to 18 March 2021 (5 half days spread over two months), may have opened a new field of accelerator science. Inspired by the first observation of gravitational waves by the LIGO and VIRGO detectors, SRGW2021 addressed the detection and/or generation of gravitational waves or other gravity effects using charged-particle storage rings or specific accelerator technologies. SRGW2021 brought together accelerator physicists, astrophysicists, light interferometric gravitational-wave detector experts, theoretical physicists, radiofrequency system specialists, etc. The SRGW2021 workshop discussed the sensitivity to gravitational waves of either the longitudinal and transverse beam response. SRGW2021 revealed that this sensitivity could be enhanced by a special optics, or by choosing specific beams (heavy ions, coasting beams, crystalline beams, etc.), and that various oscillation modes in a storage rings allow to cover a large frequency range of gravitational waves, corresponding to many different types of expected cosmic sources. SRGW also revealed that hadron storage rings could be the most powerful sources of gravitational waves at earth. Various predictions and models were proposed. Steps were made towards a future roadmap, and a workshop summary report compiled and posted on Zenodo. A summary of detection and generation options presented at the Workshop is shown in Fig. 5. Following the SRGW2021 workshop discussions started between Imperial College, King’s College and CERN, in preparation for installing an atomic-beam interferometer inside one of the LHC access shafts at CERN. The Workshop has been recently summarized by an article on the CERN Courier scientific magazine⁴.

⁴ “Accelerators meet gravitational waves”, <https://cerncourier.com/a/accelerators-meet-gravitational-waves/>

Fig. 5: Accelerator detection (and generation) options emerging from SRGW2021

SRGW201 concluded a cycle of events devoted to the exploration of far-future accelerators options – earlier WP6.6 workshops had addressed photon colliders, Gamma Factory, muon colliders, and the use of crystals or nanotubes for acceleration or bending of particle beams.

An article summarizing the APEC studies on the possible trapping of neutral molecules in the electromagnetic beam field, to explain a performance limitation experienced at the LHC, was highlighted as Editors’ Suggestion by the journal *Physical Review - Accelerators and Beams*. Also, during P3, an ARIES WP6 article on “Modern and Future Colliders” was published in the journal *Reviews of Modern Physics* (Rev. Mod. Phys. 93, 015006 (2021)).

In March 2021, WP6 conducted a community survey. The survey invitation was sent to 388 different participants from six ARIES exploratory workshops. A total of 94 experts responded. The result was used in the preparation for ARIES Deliverable D6.5 “White List of Far Future Options”, where the highest priority and importance are assigned to the proton-based muon collider, plasma acceleration, positron-based muon collider, and crystal or nanostructure acceleration. All of these are envisioned to be realized on a 20-year time scale. These also are the four options offering the highest potential return to society, with plasma and crystal/nanostructure acceleration at the top, followed by the two muon colliders. A further 20-year option is detecting gravitational waves (GWs) using storage rings.

For the coming 10-15 years, the community expects to see the advent of high-energy high-current accelerators with energy recovery, deployment of crystal bending and the Gamma Factory. These options are considered the most feasible and of lowest risk. Lowest priority and lowest potential return to society is attributed to the photon collider, to crystalline beams, to “Moessbauer acceleration” using photon entanglement, to gravitational wave generation using accelerators, and to non-electromagnetic acceleration of focusing.

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P3 reporting period, WP6 had one deliverable and three milestones that were all achieved:

- D6.5 - White list of ranked far-future accelerator options (M46)
- MS30 - Strategies for e-cloud mitigation in future accelerators (M40)
- MS31 - Identification & prioritization of mitigation approaches (M40)
- MS32 - Feasibility of an Open Data Infrastructure for accelerator reliability (M44)

1.6 WP7 RINGS WITH ULTRA-LOW EMITTANCE

In Period 3, WP7 organised the 8th LER (Low-Emittance Rings) Workshop on 26-30 October 2020 INFN-LNF foreseen at INFN Frascati Laboratories but finally held remotely (<https://agenda.infn.it/event/20813/overview>). Despite the problems with the covid-19 pandemic, the virtual workshop has proven to be very popular in the community with 160 participants doubling the usual in-person attendance. The sessions covered progress report from facilities, LER design, commissioning and operation, collective effects and feedback, vacuum technology, alignment and lattice tuning, injection systems, instrumentation, and magnet technology. Highlights of the workshop were the report about the commissioning of the ESRF-EBS and SIRIUS that was completed in 2020. In particular the ESRF EBS reached the design parameters within the foreseen time frame in August 2020. The success of these machines has opened up a new era for synchrotron light sources, proving that ultra-low emittance designs are workable. The workshop reported also on the large number of new projects that are currently under design or received funding in EU and around the world. The progress in the design and analysis of such rings is such that, presently, all new projects are aiming at producing electron beam emittances below the 100 pm, even in relatively modest circumference rings. There was also substantial representation of industrial partners with 5 talks in different sessions covering vacuum and injection. The presentation on indico provide a complete and well referenced overview of the activity in the field, pointing to the latest development in the design and in the R&D of such rings. There was general consensus that the networking activity should continue and supported in upcoming EU projects. In fact, the 8th Low Emittance Ring Workshop celebrated the the 10th anniversary of this series of event and the support of ARIES has been instrumental in allowing these activities to continue.

Together with the preparation of the Workshop, the Network WP7 has prepared the final summary of 4 years of investigations within ARIES that was published in the Deliverable Report D7.4.

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P3 reporting period, WP7 had one deliverable and this was achieved:

- D7.4 - Final report on the Rings with Ultra-Low Emittance network (M46)

1.7 WP14 PROMOTING INNOVATION

WP14 had already almost fully completed the entire scope of its work plan at the end of P2, having submitted all but one Milestones and one Deliverables that had been delayed because of the Covid pandemics. During P3 the few remaining activities to be performed were:

- the final reporting of the Proof of Concept (PoC) projects,
- the organization of the second academia-industry workshop,
- and the finalization of the deliverable D14.5.

It was decided to profit of the ARIES 4th Annual Meeting to deliver the PoC final reports during a half-day session, profiting of the main event organization to provide more visibility to the investigations done, and to create opportunities of synergies and fruitful interactions with the extended ARIES community. The presentations took place (by video) on 22 April 2021 and were followed by a “lessons learned” presentation and discussion. The slides of the presentations are available at <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1008814/timetable/#20210422.detailed>.

The outcome of the PoC “experiment” has been considered very satisfactory by both organisers and participants. All beneficiaries agree that PoC provided timely resources, deployed in short amount of time, as well as networks, visibility, competences, and know-how from cross-cutting domains to innovative promising projects. Among the elements to be improved, the participants mentioned the fact that proponents and evaluators should work better to identify and select actions with “market value”. The level of effort needs to be up to the challenge, while monitoring and reporting is adequate and considered critical to address problems and steer direction.

The second academy-meets-industry event on RAMI (Reliability, Availability, Maintainability, and Inspectability) was supposed to be held in Daresbury, UK, in M36, and STFC (hosting organization of the event), together with CERN and Wigner institute, had planned the organization, mobilized key speakers and disseminated already the agenda. Unfortunately, the event had to be last minute cancelled as effect of the COVID-19 in-person meeting limitations and of the travel restrictions imposed and still prescribed by many organizations and institutions, including CERN. The event took finally place online on 25 June 2021 (Figure 6 presents the Workshop poster). Agenda and contributions can be found at <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1048728/page/22713-outline-agenda> and <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1048728/contributions/>, respectively.

Fig. 6: RAMI Workshop poster

In the past years ARIES has organised topical discussions on Reliability of particle accelerators. With this new workshop we have extended the discussions to the full RAMI elements, which includes as well Availability, Maintainability and Inspectability of particle accelerators and also embracing fusion nuclear plants and Accelerator Driven Systems. The workshop has gathered participants from several international and national science facilities, with academics and industry sharing their specific examples of good practices. Two industries have been presenting their ideas, and five national and international laboratories were represented and participating.

The Deliverable D14.5, reporting the final results on the Industrialisation of REDNet Accelerator Timing System for Industrial and Medical Applications has been completed and submitted.

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P3 reporting period, WP7 had one deliverable and this was achieved:

- D14.5 - Real-time Event Distribution Network brought to openly accessible “product grade level (M46)

1.8 WP15 THIN FILMS FOR SUPERCONDUCTING RF CAVITIES

1.8.1 Task 15.1: Coordination and communication

The Covid-19 related restrictions reduced the level of activities in the WP15 partner's laboratories, some laboratories have been close for a period between 2 and 6 months. However, the partners managed to continue the most critical activities, although at reduced level. Coordination of WP15 activities in such a challenging period required frequent communications to solve current problems, to adjust schedules, to discuss experimental details and results etc. Over last year, all WP15 meetings were organised as virtual (Vidyo or ZOOM) meetings. Three meeting were a full WP15 meeting there each partner has reported on a progress on all activities followed by a Q&A and a discussion. Other informal (cross-task and task related) meetings were organised practically on a monthly basis.

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P2 reporting period, Task 15.1 had one deliverable to achieve: D15.4 "Final report on thin film technology" - [ACHIEVED](#)

1.8.2 Task 15.2: Substrate surface preparation

The main part of the Task 15.2 in the third period was polishing activity on QPR samples at INFN. Following the results obtained in the first period on planar samples, two polishing techniques were adapted to QPR samples: chemical polishing (also known as SUBU5) and electropolishing (EP). Before proceeding with the polishing treatments, several experiments were carried out, to solve some problems such as: enormous pitting, machining lines, point and defects, (dis)uniformity, oxidations, quantity of material removed and others. This has been reported in Deliverable Report D15.3. Figure 7 shows a QPR sample after EP, ready for the coating process.

In months M37-M48, the protocol has been adapted to re-treat the QPR after the coating and RF test to produce a fresh copper substrate on the top ready for a new coating (see the QPR sample workflow Fig. 8). In particular, mechanical polishing has been avoided and 3 more surface treatments have been added: indium removal, Nb chemical stripping and persulfate etching. The details have been reported in Deliverable Report D15.4.

In total, during the reporting period the earlier deposited films were removed and copper surfaces were successfully polished on 5 QPR samples. After polishing at INFN the QPR samples undergo the standard workflow of experiments with WP15 partners as shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: QPR B4 sample after EP electropolishing treatment.

Figure 8: QPR sample workflow. For each process is reported the treatment facility. Indium removal and persulfate etching processes are included in “Nb chemical stripping” step.

Figure 9: Overview of the field of full flux penetration (B_{fp}) for the Nb films on Cu.

The effect of Cu substrate polishing with different procedure on Nb films has been investigated in 1st year of ARIES WP15 (see Deliverable Report 15.1). The sample have been characterised with surface

characterisation techniques at the same lab there deposited, then their magnetisation as a function of applied magnetic field at 4.2 K were studied at VSM at IEE. First entry field, B_{en} , has been used to compare the deposited films. New results for the same samples were obtained with a new field penetration facility **at STFC** (the details of the experimental facility are described in related section below). The field of full flux penetration (B_{fp}) for various Nb/Cu samples obtained with this facility are shown in Fig. 9 as a function of sample temperature. The main result is that the highest B_{fp} obtained were on substrates polished with SUBU5 or EP, while the lowest correspond to EP+SUBU5. Thus, these B_{fp} measurements confirm the earlier B_{en} results obtained with VSM and provides more evidence that SUBU5 or EP should be preferred procedures for copper polishing.

1.8.3 Task 15.3: Thin film deposition and analysis

1.8.3.1 Developing of non-Nb SC thin film coating and SIS structures

The task of deposition was pursued by STFC, INFN and University of Siegen. At the beginning of the project, it was decided to use the deposition methods that are available at all three centres. Therefore, planar DC and HiPIMS magnetron deposition were used. In the third period the developing of superconducting films was focused on further developing of non-Nb superconducting thin films and multilayer systems: superconductor-insulator-superconductor (SIS) and superconductor-superconductor (SS). This required determining the best deposition parameters for synthesising higher T_c superconducting materials such as Nb₃Sn (System 1), NbN (System 2), NbTiN (System 3) and V₃Si as an alternative superconducting thin film to be used in either single layer or SIS formation (see Deliverable Reports 15.2-15.4). It should be noted, that unlike Nb all other alternative SRF material can only be used in SRF cavity in the form of thin film structure. The knowledge and experience from earlier periods has been employed for depositing Nb films as a base and non-Nb superconducting materials as another superconducting layer in SS and SIS structure.

At STFC:

Having identified the optimum deposition parameters for depositing high T_c superconductor of Nb₃Sn and NbTiN, a series of multilayer SIS structures were deposited with a substrate temperature of 650 °C. When Nb₃Sn is deposited in a multilayer SIS structure, the magnetisation loop shows no hysteresis in the loop, which can be associated with the protective effect of the multilayer, which reduces the sensitivity to flux pinning. The first penetration field was determined to be $B_{en} = 108$ mT for copper and $B_{en} = 130$ mT on sapphire. The B_{c2} for both cases was determined to be above 16 T.

For NbTiN SIS multilayer as shown in Fig. 10, a series of samples were deposited keeping the deposition parameters constant for all layers and changing only the thickness of the layers and number of top insulating/superconducting multilayer. The best results were found to be when the underlying Nb layer was at the largest thickness of the series and independent of the number of SIS multilayer and their respective thickness.

Figure 10: (a) the x-section SEM of a triple multilayer NbTiN in SIS structure, (b) corresponding EDS depicting each layer composition, (c) the DC magnetisation loop at $T = 4.22$ K.

At USI:

A series of different SIS films were deposited. These films all utilised a Nb/AlN/NbN structure and were deposited onto electropolished Cu substrates. The coatings were concluded in a staggered fashion based on the step-wise improvements made to both the Nb and NbN layers.

Following the initial study of SIS films deposited onto Cu using DCMS and reported in in Deliverable Report D15.3, two sets of SIS samples were deposited, both using a HiPIMS Nb base layer and DCMS NbN layers. Two different NbN “recipes” were used for the outer shielding layer, one with high T_c and one with high B_{en} , while also investigating the role of the shielding layer thickness. The AlN layer was again maintained at 30 nm with the NbN layer varying between 100 and 250 nm. The

superconducting results indicated a definite split between the two series with those deposited with the high B_{en} , NbN film proving to be superior. The results also exhibited specific entry field maximums for each series, related to the shielding layer thickness, pointing to an optimum thickness as previously reported in D15.1. The T_c values of the NbN layers showed an increase with increasing thickness, but were similar to those of the original, single layer films. These results highlighted the importance of using high B_{en} films for the shielding layer but did not improve upon the entry field values obtained with the pure HiPIMS Nb film.

A final series of SIS samples were produced using the HiPIMS NbN recipe with the highest B_{en} while also investigating the effects of AlN and NbN film thicknesses. The AlN was set at either 8 or 30 nm, with NbN layer thicknesses between 75 and 250 nm deposited on both. The superconducting performance of these films was consistently higher than those of the previous SIS film series and surpassed that of the HiPIMS Nb film in some instances as shown in Fig. 11. Again, a specific maximum in the entry field was found for a specific NbN film thickness, further pointing to its role in effectively shielding the underlying Nb film. The thickness of the NbN film which led to the highest entry field was thicker for the HiPIMS deposition compared to DCMS, indicating the cleaner state of the film, in line with previously produced theoretical models.

Figure 11: The normalised magnetic moments and magnetisation loop of Nb and NbN in single and multilayer structure deposited with DC and HiPIMS.

1.8.3.2 QPR sample deposition

Finally, all these knowledge and experience obtained during developing of both Nb and non-Nb SC thin film coating were employed for depositing on the QPR samples for the following test at the RF conditions. This required modifying existing facility at University of Siegen (USI), see Fig 12 (a) or building new dedicated deposition facilities at STFC and INFN, see Fig 12 (b) and (c).

For Nb deposition on a QPR sample at STFC, a dedicated deposition system was built and placed in a portable ISO5 clean room. The system is comprised of RGA to monitor the vacuum quality at all stages, retractable 3' magnetron and view port for observing the surface of the QPR. The results the QPR samples coated with Nb at STFC and USI and tests with RF at HZB were reported in Deliverable Report 15.3 and Periodic Report 2.

Figure 12: (a) A QPR sample inside the deposition chamber at University of Siegen, (b) a QPR sample inside the deposition chamber and after Nb film deposition at STFC, (c) a QPR sample deposition facility at INFN

In the reported period, several test samples have been deposited at INFN and STFC to optimise the deposition system, but no QPR sample has been deposited and RF tested. Unfortunately, a restrictions related to covis-19 inteapted the laboratory activities in spring-summer 2020 and alows only a reduced level of activity unil the end of ARIES projects. This results in a reduced number of QPR samples that have been deposited by the partners and RF tested at HZB. Thus, the QPR sample

deposition facilities at STFC and INFN were tested and are ready for samples, but they have not been used during a reported period as a number of QPR samples and the RF testing periods were limited, so, these facilities will be used in following months outside the ARIES project.

However, three QPR samples were coated at USI with different SIS structures to investigate the effects of the AlN layer thickness, see Table 1. For comparison, a sample prepared at Jefferson Lab (JLab) and measured with the HZB QPR prior to ARIES is included as well. The first ARIES multilayer sample was prepared by DC magnetron sputtering, as described before. This technique was also used for the JLab sample. The second and third ARIES samples were prepared by HiPIMS - these samples were coated in one run without an intermediate baseline test. Besides the manufacturing technique, the main difference between the samples was the chosen thickness of the AlN insulator layer.

Table 1: List of QPR samples coated with SIS structures.

	SIS films tested	Structure	Baseline	Production
JLab SIS	NbTiN – AlN – Nb(bulk)	75nm – 15 nm – bulk Nb	Yes	JLab, DCMS
ARIES 1st SIS	NbN – AlN – Nb(film)/Cu	197nm – 35 nm – 3 μm Nb	Yes	Siegen, DCMS
ARIES 2nd SIS	NbN – AlN – Nb(film)/Cu	180nm – 8 nm – 4 μm Nb	No	Siegen, HiPIMS
ARIES 3ed SIS	NbN – AlN – Nb(film)/Cu	180nm – 24 nm – 4 μm Nb	No	Siegen, HiPIMS

1.8.4 Task 15.4: Superconductivity evaluation

Task 15.4 comprises AC/DC and RF testing of samples that were manufactured and characterized in the preceding Tasks 15.2 and 15.3.

RF testing of QPR samples at HZB

Multilayer structures

The surface resistance values versus temperature of all samples are plotted in Fig. 13. It can be seen that HiPIMS coated samples generally exhibit a better (i.e. smaller) surface resistance. As a general trend, the surface resistance is better, the thinner the insulator layer is. The likely explanation for this behaviour is that the dielectric losses in the insulator layer are proportional to the layer thickness. Hence, the measurements suggest that the impact of dielectric losses cannot be neglected in multilayer films and making the insulator as thin as possible is mandatory for multilayered structures.

Since the purpose of the insulating layer is suppressing the proximity effect between the superconducting layers (and to avoid a Josephson junction between them), any value above ~1 nm for the insulator layer is acceptable - which makes the feasibility of the coating the limiting factor.

Note, that this phenomenon could only be seen in true RF measurements at realistic fields, but not in the DC measurements.

The arguably most significant result was achieved with the ARIES-3rd-SIS sample, which showed low residual resistance (about 45 nΩ) and low “Q-slope” or field dependent increase of surface resistance, equivalent to bulk Nb (see Fig. 14). The residual resistance of the bulk Nb, presented here was about 23 nΩ. The only drawback of the film was that the maximum achieved field for NbN top layer was about 35 mT.

Figure 13: Surface resistance as a function of temperature of a series of SIS multilayer samples.

For further improvement, also with respect to the continuation of the work in IFAST, the following conclusions can be made:

1. Use as thin as possible insulator layers.
2. HiPIMS works better.

In the future the following topics should be addressed:

- A. The limitation of the maximum field needs to be studied.
- B. Further decrease residual resistance.

One of the main scopes of the ARIES WP15 has been successfully achieved with these measurements: A processing chain for SRF thin film samples has been established, where every partner contributes

Figure 14: R_s vs field for the HiPIMS made samples in comparison with a bulk Nb sample.

manufacturing steps according to their laboratories’ expertise. The lessons learned from the preparation, materials and DC characterisation of the films have been applied to QPR samples, which

were as the final step RF-tested in the quadrupole resonator. The RF tests reveal important information that cannot be obtained by other means, such as, for example, the RF surface resistance of the sample. Also, due to the considerable RF-active area of a QPR sample, the QPR measurements reveal information about the upscaling of the coating procedure which will eventually have to be extended to curved surfaces of cavities.

A direct result of the QPR measurements is the insight that the insulating layer in SIS samples needs to be made as small as possible in order to avoid dielectric losses.

Another outcome was the insight, that the non-monotonic features sometimes observed in surface resistance versus temperature samples were caused by poor film quality rather than unknown physical effects, and can therefore be used as a criterion for a poor film in the future.

1.8.4.1 QPR test of laser treated Nb thin films

In first three years of ARIES WP15, it was demonstrated that the laser treatment provided **at RTU** on the Nb thin film deposited on Cu substrate could increase the adhesion of Nb/Cu structures, the ductility and grain size of the coating, and the defects between grains (pinholes) can be eliminated. The magnetisation measurements of samples performed at IEE demonstrated an improvement of superconducting properties. The details can be found in Delivery Reports 15.2 and 15.3. These results have been applied to one of QPR with earlier deposited a 3- μm thick Nb film at STFC. After the SRF testing this sample **at HZB**, the sample has been sent to RTU for laser treatment. Figure 15 shows the sample before and after laser treatment. Although after laser polishing the surface looks smoother, the RF testing does not demonstrate any improvements in SRF properties. Some local defects has been found on the Nb surface and could cause the RF losses, the nature of these defect should be studied in future. More RF tests of Laser treated Nb films should be performed in the future.

Figure 15: The QPR sample (a) before and (b) after irradiation by Nd:YAG laser at intensity $I = 75 \text{ MW/cm}^2$.

DC superconducting properties evaluation at IEE

In the DC magnetisation experiments at IEE, several sets of samples were investigated in order to compare their first flux entry field values B_{en} . The materials tested included Nb_3Sn , in single layer, double layers of $\text{Nb}_3\text{Sn}/\text{Nb}$ and in SIS layer structures of $\text{Nb}_3\text{Sn}/\text{AlN}/\text{Nb}$. The NbTi and NbTiN

materials were investigated, in single layer as well as in multilayer SIS configurations comprising 2 to 3 repetitions of the Insulator-Superconductor sequence. Utilisation of the NbN material in the SIS structures of NbN/AlN/Nb has been explored as well, in several series of samples. Here both the Nb and NbN superconducting layers were deposited using the standard DCMS method at first, then the Nb deposition method was changed to the HiPIMS, and finally both the Nb and NbN were deposited using the HiPIMS in the last series of samples.

Comparison of B_{en} values of the non-Nb films on Cu substrate is shown in Fig. 16. The highest B_{en} values are seen among the Nb₃Sn based double layer, SIS samples and among the NbN based SIS samples deposited via HiPIMS. The performance of the best other-than-Nb films is comparable to, but still somewhat lower than of the best Nb films.

Figure 16: Overview of the first flux entry fields of B_{en} for the non-Nb films on Cu substrates measured on VSM at IEE (Bratislava).

It should be noted that in the case of the multilayer films, the DC magnetisation measurements in VSM setup are not an ideal characterisation tool. The whole sample is immersed in the applied homogeneous magnetic field during the measurements and it is thus possible that the magnetic flux starts entering through the edges of the sample and in some of the sub-layers and not from the outermost layer of the multilayer structure. Local measurement methods like the third harmonic induced voltage detection or the flux penetration experiment are more suitable for multilayer films.

Magnetic field penetration measurements at STFC

The RF losses in an RF cavity coated with superconducting TF will increase as soon as the magnetic field reaches the copper substrate. Full magnetic field penetration method allows studying the superconducting TF efficiency as the magnetic screen. The earlier realisations of this method were

reported in 2nd Periodic Report. A new system shown in Figure 17 has been built, tested and is fully operational at STFC from October 2020. This facility is built with a cryogen-free cryostat, cooled with a Sumitomo RDK-408D2 cold head.

Figure 17: (a) Schematic layout and (b) operational facility for magnetic field penetration measurements.

This method is developed for magnetic field penetration measurements with planar samples (most common geometry for research). The main features of this method are the following:

- A C-shaped dipole magnet applies a DC magnetic field over a 2mm gap to ensure a homogeneous field without edge effects.
- The magnetic field ($0 \leq B \leq 600$ mT) is applied from one side of the sample and parallel to the sample surface (similar to an SRF cavity). The applied and penetrating fields are measured by Hall probe sensors.
- The method is suitable for single and multilayer (SIS) samples.
- Sample size between 35 mm × 35 mm and 52 mm × 52 mm.
- Sample temperature: 2.6 K < T < 10 K,

RF testing at STFC

An RF cavity and cryostat dedicated to the measurement of superconducting coatings on planar samples (10-cm diam. disk) at 7.8 GHz has been updated to operate with a closed-cycle refrigerator (Fig. 18). It should provide a low power RF measurements with an emphasis on fast turn-around time. During ongoing testing it is demonstrating $T_{cavity} = 3.9$ K and $T_{sample} = 3.8$ K. The facility is providing first results with bulk Nb sample. After the RF testing completed, the facility will be used for characterising the Cu samples coated with superconducting thin films.

Figure 18: A low power RF test at STFC

Contractual milestones and deliverables

In the P2 reporting period, Task 15.4 had one deliverable to achieve:

- D15.3 “Evaluation of system 3” - [ACHIEVED](#)

2. Context and objectives for the entire project

2.1 WP3 INDUSTRIAL AND SOCIETAL APPLICATIONS

The primary objectives of WP3 were to study new environmental, medical and societal applications of particle accelerators and investigate technological advances that would deliver these new applications and bring improvements to existing applications. This has been achieved for many applications and some examples are given here.

- (1) Marine diesel engine exhaust gas treatment. Following initial studies that were performed at the INCT, a Proof of Concept project was funded by ARIES and performed tests on a marine diesel engine by a team including INCT and FEP. These have demonstrated that the technique works and has the potential for wide-scale use.
- (2) A pilot plant to demonstrate the use of electron beams for treating sewage sludge is in the process of being built and should be in operation soon. Studies have shown that there should be a significant increase in bio-gas production from anaerobic digestion and an improvement in the quality of the fertiliser produced.
- (3) Studies of the use of electron beams for treating the ballast water from ships, for removing disease from ornamental bulbs and for preserving valuable water damaged documents have also been done by the INCT.
- (4) In collaboration with others, the CNRS in Task 3.4 has led the design of accelerators able to achieve the requirements for Very High Energy Electron cancer therapy and, in particular, for FLASH therapy.
- (5) In Task 3.5, CIEMAT has completed modifications to the AMIT cyclotron to enable testing and these tests are imminent. This cyclotron could bring a sea-change in the production of PET imaging radioisotopes. HUD has designed a compact, high beam current accelerator for the production of therapeutic and theragnostic radioisotopes.

All deliverables and milestones planned to be achieved in WP3 have been delivered, with only minor delays in two cases, one due to COVID-19.

2.2 WP4 EFFICIENT ENERGY MANAGEMENT

This NA federates different research centres that perform internal programmes aimed at analysing strategies to save energy. It concentrates on promoting, following and coordinating clear technological solutions towards increasing the efficiency of four critical accelerator sub-systems: Radio-Frequency power sources, superconducting accelerating cavities, pulsed magnets and targets.

Besides the work on concrete goals for each task, also networking workshops with international participation were held, some of them focused on specific topics but also two workshops with a very broad content related to sustainability of large research infrastructures.

The results achieved by the Tasks, fully in line with their initial objectives, were:

- Design and simulation work of a 12 GHz high efficiency klystron radio-frequency power supply (called “klystron”) has been completed, obtaining 65% efficiency in realistic simulations.
- Monte Carlo simulations on an efficient neutron source have been completed, including: target and moderator geometry optimization, multi-physics simulations of radiation transport, thermomechanical simulations to consider target/moderator assembly including 2-phase D₂O, and new type of 2-phase simulations resulting in a concept proposals for the SINQ facility at PSI.
- Experimental and theoretical work on flux trapping and magnetic shielding, resulting in much improved understanding of magnetic shielding and in the definition and assembling of a test device for Niobium samples.
- A prototype pulsed quadrupole power supply has been set up equipped with a specially-designed circuit recovering 28% of the energy from pulse to pulse.

2.3 WP5 EUROPEAN NETWORK FOR NOVEL ACCELERATORS

The European Network for Novel Accelerators (EuroNNAC), as WP5 in ARIES, had the goal of providing a common discussion forum and self-coordination for the field of novel accelerators, focusing on ultra-high gradient concepts, in particular plasma-based and dielectric machines. It aimed at bringing together a high number of experiments and groups involved in Europe and world-wide, pursuing the goal of bringing those novel accelerators to application readiness, exploiting their unique potential for accelerator facilities with reduced size and cost, while offering several unique benefits (for example ultra-fast science and high contrast medical imaging).

WP5 organized two European Advanced Accelerator Concepts workshops (EAAC), provided support to young scientists, formulated input to the European Strategy for Particle Physics, supported the EuPRAXIA community project up to its placement on the ESFRI roadmap update 2021 and spawned off a European Expert Panel for proposing a European Strategy on Plasma & Laser Accelerators for Particle Physics.

2.4 WP6 ACCELERATOR PERFORMANCE AND CONCEPTS

The wider goals of WP6 were:

- To advance on beam quality control in Hadron Storage Rings and Synchrotrons, by identifying processes causing performance degradation, ranking them according to their relative importance, and finally by identifying and prioritizing mitigation approaches, in collaboration with Technology JRAs (electron-lenses, thin films, etc.).
- To establish a standard body of Reliability, Availability, Maintainability, Serviceability (RAMS) knowledge for particle accelerator applications, to compile and rank existing RAMS standards, methods and practices in major laboratories, to analyse optimal RAMS characteristics for particle accelerator systems, and to spread best RAMS practices to

- introduce a common baseline, and assess the feasibility of an Open Data Infrastructure for accelerator reliability.
- To review existing strategies and methods for beam-impedance assessments and impedance models, proposing and evaluating novel methods to reduce accelerator impedance, mitigations for electron-cloud at future accelerators, and conceptual design of advanced beam feedback systems for future machines.
 - To expand synergies between proposed future Energy Recovery Linac (ERL) projects and operating or close to operation linacs/recirculating linacs and ERLs in Europe, establishing a parameter database for the various facilities, examining innovative and alternative ERL approaches, working out synergies between linac developers and source developers for optimum beam quality, and identifying outstanding questions and prioritized R&D guidelines.
 - Explore far future accelerator concepts and their feasibility. Analyse the potential of crystals for charged-particle bending or particle acceleration, the development of advanced photon colliders, including gamma-gamma and photon-nucleon colliders, assess advanced muon-collider concepts without ionization cooling, assess the potential use of large storage rings for gravitational wave detection or generation, assess and rank a basket of future concepts with regard to “future feasibility” and physics cases, producing a white list of ranked future options.

In this respect, the main achievements of the WP have been:

Reviving and advancing the designs of a muon collider, either proton based with advanced ingredients like parametric ionization cooling, or based on positron annihilation without cooling, and helping to prepare the corresponding input to the European Strategy Update (ESU) 2019/20, which then indeed endorsed R&D on muon colliders. This will be pursued in I.FAST, through a dedicated working group and/or European R&D panel, and the US Snowmass process.

Launching pioneering discussions of using storage rings and accelerator technologies for the detection or generation of gravitational waves, which may gather significant momentum in the coming years, and already stimulated concrete plans for a first experiment in an LHC access shaft.

Cementing the case for energy-recovery based colliders, with input to the ESU19/20 process, and establishment of ERL R&D guidelines [ARIES D6.4], which highlight and elaborate the goals for (1) test facilities, (2) beam dynamics & diagnostics, (3) electron sources & injectors, (4) superconducting RF systems, incl. high loaded Q cavity operation; HOMs, HOM damping & high current operation; and high Q_0 cavity performance. The ESU 19/20 has supported further R&D on energy-recovery based colliders and accelerators. The WP6 results will also inform the R&D program for the PERLE test facility at IJClab and other European ERL projects (MESA, BerlinPRO, DIANA,...), and the special ERL R&D Panel that was set up in response to the ESU recommendations.

Developing the design, feasibility demonstration and possible operation modes for the proposed Gamma Factory based on partially stripped heavy-ion beams in the LHC colliding with suitable laser pulses, which became one of the inputs to the European Strategy Process, and is pursued through a multi-step experimental demonstration process at the CERN SPS and LHC.

Making the case for, revealing the advances of, and preparing future R&D paths for the application of bent crystals (which have now been included in the HL-LHC collimation baseline) and for crystal/nanostructure acceleration, which is an interesting and possibly more promising alternative to plasma acceleration, with potential gradients up to a factor of 1000 higher than in a plasma.

Defining optimal RAMS characteristics for accelerators [ARIES D6.2], covering the availability critical systems and availability model (example FCC-ee); measures to improve reliability of power converters, RF system, and electrical distribution (lead causes of unavailability for CERN's normal conducting machines); operations modelling platform (example FCC-hh) for allocating availability goals to different sub-machines, and fault-tolerant system design. The Accelerator Reliability Information System (ARIS) was developed as a proof of concept open data infrastructure for accelerator reliability.

Assessing performance limitations in hadron synchrotrons [D6.1], where beam loss, single-bunch instabilities, and nonlinearities figure prominently, and a review and ranking of mitigation measures [MS31, D6.3], which included Landau octupoles, bunch-by-bunch feedback, optimised tunes, and tailored slippage factor; novel techniques emerging; for impedance effects, mechanical design optimization, feedback systems, advanced coatings (HTS,...); and for space charge, a number of other mitigations, such a reducing the peak charge density.

Ranking of (far-)future accelerator options [D6.5], which will serve as a future roadmap, with priority advocated for (1) energy recovery linacs, crystal bending, Gamma Factory; (2) muon collider(s), plasma & crystal & nanostr. acceleration, gravitational wave detection. These are broadly aligned with the ESU19/20 (muon colliders, plasma, energy recovery), but add the crystal bending, crystal acceleration, Gamma Factory, and the use of storage rings for gravitational wave detection.

2.5 WP7 RINGS WITH ULTRA-LOW EMITTANCE (RULE)

The wider objectives of WP7 were:

- Organise the general workshops and other relevant networking activities for the community of ultra-low emittance rings;
- exchange scientific information and share experience for the technology of injection systems, including septa, kickers and pulsers; explore the impact of injection system parameters in the optimisation of the rings dynamic aperture and the design of the injectors;
- analyse beam dynamics and technology for ultra-low emittance rings, in particular design of innovative magnets and the impact to beam dynamics, impact of two-stream instabilities on beam dynamics, design of vacuum systems including mitigation techniques, design and experimental tests of main and harmonic RF systems for various bunch structures.
- support exchange and collaboration between low emittance rings for beam tests covering beam dynamics and technology issues and support efforts in the new rings commissioning but also new operating modes of existing rings.

The key achievements have been:

WP7 has supported networking activities and seven Workshops, several of which specifically dedicated to the specific aspects the design and technology of low emittance rings subsystems:

- First topical workshop on injection and injection systems for ultra-low emittance rings, Bessy-II, Berlin (Germany), August 2017.
- 7th General Low Emittance Ring network workshop, CERN, January 2018.
- Topical workshop on diagnostics for ultra-low emittance rings, Chilton (UK), April 2018.
- Topical workshop on commissioning of ultra-low emittance ring, KIT, Karlsruhe (Germany), February 2018.
- Second topical workshop on injection and injection systems for ultra-low emittance rings, TWISS, PSI, Villigen (Switzerland), February 2019.
- Advanced Low-Emittance Ring Technology (ALERT2019), with topical theme “rings with small apertures”, in Ioannina (Greece), July 2019.
- 8th General Low Emittance Ring network workshop, (virtual) INFN, Frascati, October 2020.

These workshops have been well attended, usually by ~80 delegates for the general workshop and ~40 for the topical workshop, with a notable spike to 160 delegates for the virtual workshop in October 2020.

For injection schemes, WP7 has analysed and promoted schemes based on new beam physics ideas, on technological advance in the design of kickers and striplines and on the development of new pulsed power modulators. Use of new kickers with zero field on-axis (non-linear kicker, NLK) has emerged, requiring the joint development of new injection schemes.

Innovative magnet systems for quadrupole gradients approaching 100 T/m have been analysed and compared, allowing a reduction in the emittance by a factor of 7. The vacuum system has been analysed and miniaturised compared to previous design, with a notable involvement of industries.

Collective effects have been analysed, including semi-analytical characterisation of surface impedance, experimental characterisation of coating materials, and effect of harmonic cavities.

WP7 has supported the experimental tests on a number of critical points for the design and operation of low emittance rings. These include joint experimental sessions taken place for a beam test and a workshop aiming to the beam tests and commissioning of LERs. Tests included beam injection and extraction, insertion devices, orbit feedbacks, low- and negative momentum compaction factors, done at several European facilities, followed by a joint measurement campaign at the three key facilities KARA, SOLEIL and SLS. A dedicated Workshop allowed exchanging experience on past and ongoing beam commissioning activities of low emittance rings.

2.6 WP14 PROMOTING INNOVATION

The specific objectives and achievements of WP14 are:

- promoting innovation in the accelerator community by evaluating, assessing and developing technology inside ARIES. To implement this objective, it has been set-up a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) scheme that has provided resources and visibility to innovative and promising technologies

- increase the effectiveness of market-pull initiatives. To this scope has been set-up an Industry Advisory Board, charged to advise the project management and to support initiatives related to PoC.
- facilitate the industries-academia collaboration and technical exchanges. To this scope it has been organized industrial workshops on ARIES technologies with potential industrial applications.
- support specific co-innovation actions with industry. To this scope have been implemented 3 industrial projects aimed at the development of higher performance and lower cost high-temperature superconducting cables, of new graphitic materials and coatings, and of a standardized multi-platform timing system.

2.7 WP 15 THIN FILMS FOR SUPERCONDUCTING RF CAVITIES

The aim of WP15 was to intensify systematic studies and development of the coating technology of superconducting materials to enable the production of superconducting coated RF cavities with Q(E) characteristics better than for the bulk Niobium ones. The main emphasis is on a systematic study of correlation between:

- substrate surface preparation,
- deposition parameters for superconducting materials Nb, NbN, Nb₃Sn, NbTiN and SIS deposited on Cu substrate,
- film structure, morphology, chemistry, phase,
- AC and DC superconductivity parameters, such as T_c, H_c, H_{fp}, H_{sh}, RRR
- the behaviour at RF conditions with the test cavities at CERN, HZB and STFC.

The main achievement can be listed as:

- Five polishing techniques for Cu have been tested with Nb films: SUBU5 and EP have demonstrate best results and have been adopted for the following.
- Development of non-Nb superconducting films on small samples were achieved, depositing and characterising NbN, Nb₃Sn, NbTiN films as well as SIS structures, and evaluation SC properties with small samples of VSM and MFPP;
- Evaluation of Nb films at the RF conditions was successfully performed, based on new QPR sample design, development and application of a new QRR sample polishing, deposition of 10 QPR samples with Nb and SIS: Nb/AlN/NbN and Nb/AlN/Nb₃Sn. This was the first QPR results for SIS structures.
- New technologies were developed for the laser treatment of Cu substrate and Nb films, and Magnetic field penetration facility (MFPPF).

These achievements enable progressing to the next stage, developing a real cavity prototype coated with non-Nb superconducting TF and SIS structures.

3. Main scientific and technical results (Entire project)

3.1 WP3 INDUSTRIAL AND SOCIETAL APPLICATIONS (ISA)

3.1.1 Low energy electron beam applications: new technology development

This Task has prepared a comprehensive report on current applications of electron beam accelerators up to 10 MeV used in R&D programs and industrial implementations. The material will be the basis for future perspectives of accelerator design improvements and their role in the enhancement of the radiation technology applications share of the global economy and social well-being.

Two types of accelerator technology have been investigated during this period: one at low beam energy (less than 300 keV) and one at the highest applicable electron beam energy accepted for electron beam (eb) processing (10 MeV). The layout of first of these, the ILU-6 facility at INCT (with adjustable electron energy up to 2 MeV), is presented in Figure 19.

Fig. 19 ILU-6 eb facility at INCT

They were studied for a promising new application: radiation-induced grafting (10 MeV), surface microbial decontamination (300 keV) and sanitation of old library books, manuscripts, archives and cultural heritage art crafts (10 MeV).

FEP has shown that automated LEEI (low energy electron irradiation) can be used to inactivate various organisms in liquid solution by delivering exact doses in a wide range, which renders the method suitable for numerous fields within biotechnology. Bacteria (*E. coli*, *B. cereus*) and viruses (Influenza A, RSV and Zika virus) were efficiently inactivated by the automated LEEI-processes, and the doses necessary were similar to those obtained with other ionizing radiation technologies, with viruses being generally more resistant than bacteria due to their lower content of nucleic acids. Even *Bacillus*-spores, which are known to be highly resistant to radiation and other sterilization methods, were readily inactivated by LEEI, although at much higher doses than *E. coli* cells. On the other hand, the antigenic material was well conserved and allowed recognition by antibodies or hemagglutination

of erythrocytes. DNA-fragments generated by LEEI were still long enough to be detected in a diagnostic PCR for *B. cereus*. These findings are in line with data from other studies showing that ionizing radiation generates fragments of approx. 0.5 to 1 kilobases. Therefore, liquids containing pathogens can be treated with LEEI and thereafter analysed with standard diagnostic tools. This has important implications, e.g. for the analysis of potentially contagious patient samples containing highly pathogenic microbes which currently need to be handled at a high containment level for the purposes of diagnostic analysis or need to be shipped to irradiation facilities. Currently, chemical inactivation, often in combination with heat treatment, is the standard procedure for inactivating potentially contagious pathogens in e.g. patient samples. The addition of chemicals is time-consuming and complicates downstream assays due to chemical modification of nucleic acids and/or proteins in the sample. Other procedures for sterilizing liquids e.g. blood products of human origin used in transfusion medicine are usually treated with ionizing radiation, mainly UV-irradiation.

The major drawback is the requirement for photosensitizing chemicals for efficient inactivation with UV, due to the low penetration depth of the UV-irradiation. Another major advantage of LEEI compared to existing irradiation methods (gamma- and X-rays, high energy electrons) is the lack of significant considerable shielding requirements. Currently it is not possible to perform ionizing radiation for pathogen inactivation inside a standard biological laboratory. As a consequence, the material must be transported to specialized irradiation facilities, which makes the technology very complicated or even not feasible for many purposes.

In contrast, existing self-shielded LEEI-devices for surface treatment have a footprint of approx. 2 square-meters, and the modules for generating the liquid film, described in this study, do not require significantly substantially more space. Importantly, LEEI can be operated in any standard laboratory and the operating personal does not need additional radiation-protective clothing. Another advantage of LEEI is its high dose rate, which enables fast processing. In the continuous process, exposure time of the individual pathogens to the electron beam are below one second, which enables the inactivation of several liters per hour. The dose does not have an influence on the processing duration. To achieve a similar inactivation with gamma-radiation (which has a much lower and decreasing dose rate based on the physical principles of its radioactivity and the decay of the material), the samples would need to be treated for up to several hours, depending on the pathogen.

3.1.2 Low energy electron beam applications: new applications

The main activities were related to the elaboration of the basis for ship diesel off gases electron beam treatment. The main source of air pollutants such as NO_x and SO₂ are exhaust gases generated during the combustion of fuels used in power and transport sectors. To address the adverse impacts of sulphur and nitrogen oxides from shipping emission, the maritime sector is required to find highly efficient and low cost methods of gaseous pollutant removal. New on-board installations of exhaust emission control are required and one of them may be an Electron Beam process developed by the INCT, which is one of the most effective methods of removing SO₂ and NO_x from industrial flue gases. The first implementation of this technology was demonstrated in July 2019 at Riga Shipyard, Latvia as part of an ARIES Proof-of-Concept project (Figure 20).

Fig. 20: movable electron accelerator and scrubber during the technology test at Riga shipyard

The RTU organized the experiment and secured the ship, the INCT designed and procured the scrubber (constructed by Biopolinex, Poland) and the closed water system and performed the tests and Fraunhofer FEP made available a movable electron beam accelerator mounted on trailer and contributed to the tests and to the integration.

The other field of environmental applications being developed in collaboration with ARIES is electron beam sludge hygenization. Sewage sludge is generated from wastewater treatment plant and is an organic fertilizer and is also a rich source of many macro (N, P, K) and micronutrients essential for soil. As sewage sludge still contains microbes, viruses and worm eggs, which under certain circumstances can be dangerous for human beings and animals, it must be disinfected before it is deposited on to agricultural areas. The “zero energy” hybrid process (Figure 21) combines the eb process with sludge digester supplying methane to the cogeneration plant which provides electricity for the accelerator and other equipment.

Fig. 21: zero-energy hybrid process for wastewater treatment

3.1.3 Task 3.4. Medium energy electron beams

In recent times, the idea of using very high-energy (50-250 MeV) electron (VHEE) beams for radiotherapy (RT) has gained interest, since electrons with higher energies can travel deeper into the patient. The advantages of VHEE are that the depth – dose profile from the electrons is flatter than the quasi-exponential dose given by X-rays, and in addition – in principle – the delivered electrons (which are charged) may be focused and steered in ways that are not possible for X-rays. The challenge until recently has been the difficulty in obtaining high-energy electrons using compact machines. This can now be overcome either with high-gradient (HG) cavities or by using laser-based acceleration. The work realized in the Task3.4 has been focused in particular to the study of a linac design in the energy range of interest for VHEE applications (140 MeV). The linac design based in HG S-band technology and the corresponding beamline has been studied in detail and offers the desired performances and compactness with different modes of operation including the Grid and FLASH methodologies, which are likely to represent a major breakthrough in RT.

3.1.4 Task 3.5. Radioisotope production

The increasing demand for radioisotopes requires new developments to address the challenges in the current supply market. The reduction of acquisition and running costs would foster the research of new radiopharmaceuticals as well as improving the access to the most suitable diagnostic and therapy techniques. In the framework of the activities developed in the task 3.5 of ARIES project, scientific and technical developments have been performed to improve the performance of the accelerators for radioisotope production.

Focusing on the cyclotrons as the most used type of accelerators, the optimization activities have been carried out in three fields: beam dynamics, ion sources and cooling systems. Although scientific and technical activities have been applied to the specific AMIT cyclotron, the acquired knowledge, the implementation of physical models in beam dynamics code as well as the development of different systems and facilities can be of application to other accelerators.

- Firstly, a better understanding of the beam properties during the transport and accelerator provides valuable information for the design of new machines, the optimization of their performance as well as a minimization of machine activation and the required maintenance. A comprehensive analysis of the beam dynamics of the AMIT weak focusing machine has been performed, with an optimization of the beam properties, the tune of the different variables, the analysis of component tolerances and the implementation of models for beam-residual gas and electromagnetic stripping.
- Secondly, internal sources play a vital role in compact machines. A devoted ion source test bench has been developed, allowing the characterization and optimization of the ion source behaviour.
- Finally, the efficiency of the accelerators are critical for their sustainability. Developments have been performed to minimize the dependence on external cryogenes, to reduce the impact on the overall footprint and minimize the maintenance issues. An autonomous Cryogen Cooling System (CSS) has been developed in the framework of the AMIT compact cyclotron.

3.2 WP4 EFFICIENT ENERGY MANAGEMENT

3.2.1 Networking between Large Research Infrastructure Laboratories

Two workshops in the series Energy for Sustainable Research Infrastructures (ESSRI) were co-organised by this ARIES work package. These workshops took place in November 2017 at ELI/Magurele (Romania) and in November 2019 at PSI (Switzerland). Both workshops covered a wide variety of concepts and technologies aimed at improving the sustainability of large research infrastructures. This includes for example energy management schemes, heat recovery, energy efficient technologies such as efficient RF production, low loss superconducting cavities, permanent magnets. It includes also topics that are not efficiency related, such as carbon footprint analysis, life cycle management of components or water consumption. The workshops were organised in a collaboration of the European Research Foundation ERF, CERN, ESS, ARIES-EEM and ELI, resp. PSI as the local hosts. The presentations and documentation in the form of session summaries are available on the respective internet sites.

3.2.2 High Efficiency RF Power Sources

A group at CEA performed a design study of an efficient 12 GHz klystron with about 20 MW peak power, with advice from experts at CERN, ESS and PSI. The intention was to improve its energy efficiency by more than 10% compared to commercially existing klystrons, which is roughly at 50%. CEA had already initiated a design study of a 12 GHz klystron for CLIC in the frame of EuCARD-2, and had built a prototype at 5 GHz based on a retrofit of an existing Thales TH2166 klystron. The present study builds upon the lessons learned from it. The peak power has been chosen to be between 8MW and 50 MW. Such klystron could be used for the future CompactLight FEL project.

The study focused mainly on the design of the interaction line and the multi-cell output cavity of the klystron (Fig. 22). The RF efficiency obtained with different simulation techniques is about 65%, achieving thus the initial goal for improving efficiency by more than 10 percent. As far as beam focusing is concerned, the use of alternatives solutions, less power hungry than a normal conducting solenoid, is discussed. Besides the efficiency of the tube itself, also the power dissipated in a normal conducting focusing magnet tends to be a significant contribution to the overall power consumption for low duty cycle operation. Gun and collector remain to be designed to fully complete this study.

Fig. 22: Geometry of the 12 GHz klystron design (top) and simulation of the beam particle modulation using the code CST along the tube (bottom).

3.2.3 Increasing energy efficiency of the spallation target station

In a spallation source the neutrons generated in the target are moderated to a lower and useful energy range with equivalent wavelengths of Angstroms. The moderator efficiency is a key element in the chain of converting grid power via proton beam intensity to the desired neutron flux at the experiments. In this work the optimization of the present cryogenic D₂ moderator system of the SINQ source at the Paul Scherrer Institut was studied (Figure 23). A volume that fills with D₂ vapour during operation inside the moderator vessel, called re-entrant hole (REH), was implemented in 2003 to increase the low-energy (cold) neutron flux. However, in practice no significant increase was observed and the reason was never understood in detail, a prerequisite for a future improvement. In this work, it was proven for the first time by a complex CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) simulation that the thermal power deposition of the secondary radiation from the spallation target was not intense enough to evaporate the deuterium in the REH. To arrive at this important understanding of the complex system particle transport Monte-Carlo simulations for obtaining the energy deposition were coupled with multi-phase simulations of the liquid deuterium under cryogenic conditions. Due to the complexity of the geometry and the resulting requirements for solving physical equations by discretization using the Finite Volume Method, a separation of the solid body (moderator chamber) and the fluid body (fluid) was pursued.

Fig. 23: Left: Temperature distribution of deuterium in the moderator at 1.5 mA on SINQ target. Evaporation occurs above 23.67 K. Right: Gain factor as a function of the neutron wavelength for different geometries. Above: Filled present moderator (left) and optimized genetic REH (right).

Based on the simulation results alternative geometries have been proposed to obtain the desired enhancement of the neutron flux. The aim is to decouple the re-entrant hole from the evaporation process to be independent on the beam current by designing the REH as empty evacuated box in the moderator. In the interesting wavelength range around 5 Å a gain of neutron flux around 25-30% is expected. Increasing the proton beam power from 1.4 MW to 1.8 MW would lead to the same gain but would cause a significant increase of the grid power consumption.

3.2.4 High Efficiency SRF power conversion

Superconducting accelerating resonators exhibit naturally small power losses, but these occur at cryogenic temperatures and are therefore relevant for the overall efficiency of these devices. In order to reduce such losses further it is necessary to avoid the trapping of magnetic flux in the superconductor material during cooldown. On the scale of a large CW s.c. linac the achieved quality factor of the resonators has significant impact on the total power consumption of an installation.

Even the natural earth magnetic field must be suppressed by more than an order of magnitude to obtain low losses. Within the frame of the ARIES/WP4 program, CERN measured the magnetic shielding of an empty cryomodule vessel, which is foreseen to house 4 superconducting cavities. The measurement confirmed that it is not necessary to use non-magnetic steel for this kind of application and that the existing low level of magnetisation, which is mainly due to the welds, does not need a de-magnetization campaign. Both facts contribute to a considerable cost saving for future modules of this kind.

CERN also developed and tested a new instrument, called “flux lens” for quick and reproducible measurements of the flux expulsion efficiency of Niobium sheet material. The instrument will be used for material characterisation for the crab cavities that will be used in LHC and furthermore for R&D to establish a relation between cold-working and different heat treatments of Niobium and the resulting flux expulsion efficiency. With the flux lens it is no longer necessary to build full featured test cavities out of different sheet material in order to assess it’s flux expulsion efficiency. This results in a much faster way to assess Nb sheet material and it brings substantial cost savings. Furthermore it simplifies systematic studies of flux expulsion as a function of different material treatment techniques, with the goal of lowering the surface resistance of superconducting cavities and thus lowering the power consumption of future accelerators. The method has caught the interest of the international community and JLAB (a national US laboratory) is keen to collaborate with CERN to use the flux lens for the series testing of Nb sheet material for the LCLS-II cavities.

3.2.5 Efficient operation of pulsed magnets

For some applications, for example beam transport lines in pulsed operation, it is sufficient to provide guiding magnetic fields only the time of beam passage. Thereby significant power savings can be achieved. In the scope of this work an existing prototype setup of a pulsed quadrupole magnet was improved regarding the energy efficiency. In the first part it was shown that by changing the circuit topology, making a high damping resistance unnecessary, the energy per pulse can be reduced significantly. Measurements with this improved circuit were done to verify the solution and to adapt the components in the simulation for a more realistic model behaviour.

In the second part the improved circuit was converted in an energy recovery circuit which recovers part of the energy for the next pulse. The dimensioning of the energy recovery coil regarding inductance and resistance values was discussed. Proof of principle measurements were conducted with approximately 28% energy recovery. In combination with the 80% increase in efficiency of the improved circuit, this is a substantial step in relation to the project start. Furthermore, the dimensioning of the energy recovery coil was investigated within the measurements. The results show

that no optimum can be found with the simple coil configuration used in this setup, but a design goal for the future was worked out.

3.3 WP5 EUROPEAN NETWORK FOR NOVEL ACCELERATORS

During the entire ARIES project WP5 organized two European Advanced Accelerator Concepts workshops (EAAC), provided support to young scientists, formulated input to the European Strategy for Particle Physics, supported the EuPRAXIA community project up to its placement on the ESFRI roadmap update 2021 and spawned off a European Expert Panel for proposing a European Strategy on Plasma & Laser Accelerators for Particle Physics.

3.3.1 European Advanced Accelerator Concepts Workshop (EAAC)

WP5 organized the European Advanced Accelerator Concepts workshops that were held in 2017 and 2019. Those workshops serve as a growing forum for discussions and coordination of activities. The attendance reached record levels, saturating the capacity of the workshop venue. The 4th European Advanced Accelerator Concepts Workshop (EAAC) in 2019 (Figure 24) received over 370 applications for participation with 83 student grant applications. This illustrates the dynamism of the European novel accelerator community, attracting many young scientists. Unfortunately, not all applicants could be accepted due to space limits. The total number of participants was 276, there were 16% female and 84% male participants. Participation included representatives of conventional and advanced accelerator technology, from 17 countries, mainly from Europe but also from Asia, the US and Russia. After a selection process, 47 student grants were given to young scientist to allow their participation. A special student meeting was organized to foster discussion and networking.

The European Advanced Accelerator Concepts Workshop has the mission to discuss and foster methods of beam acceleration with gradients beyond state of the art in operational facilities. The most cost effective and compact methods for generating high energy particle beams was reviewed and assessed. This includes diagnostics methods, timing technology, special needs for injectors, beam matching, beam dynamics with advanced accelerators and development of adequate simulations. Proceedings for all EAAC workshops were published after peer-review in open source format.

Fig. 24: Participants of the EAAC2019 conference on Elba in September 2019

3.3.2 Support for Students and the Simon van-der-Meer Prize

Efforts to promote the work of young scientists were further strengthened and the Simon van-der-Meer Prize for a young scientist was awarded for the first time at the EAAC 2019. In accordance with the ARIES Work Package and task 5.5, "Young Scientist Networking and Academic Standards", a special meeting has been organised during the biannual EAAC workshop, to complement the official workshop program. Within 2 hours of an open and fruitful discussion session, the particular network needs for the young scientists have been addressed in order to facilitate the exchange of information and expertise among the young colleagues. The main topics discussed were related to the training of young scientists on the topic of high gradient acceleration techniques, the issue of information exchange and, related to that, the idea to create a web-platform, optimised for and focused on the needs of students. Special attention has been put on the possibilities of students and colleagues in their early career, to gain visibility among the fast-growing community in a large and rapidly developing new field of physics.

A specialized course of the CERN accelerator school for plasma accelerators was successfully pioneered. The school welcomed 70 students from 25 different nationalities, among them, beyond Europe, China, United States and Japan. 26 lecturers from 11 countries were giving courses, seminar talks or acting as tutors for the more practical work, the so-called case studies, where the students are asked to apply what they had learned and thus to do actual design work under the leadership of experienced colleagues.

3.3.3 EuPRAXIA - the "European Plasma research Accelerator with eXcellence In Applications"

The WP5 work led to the advance and support of a new European research Infrastructure EuPRAXIA. The EuPRAXIA project successfully completed its Conceptual Design Report in October 2019. For the next project phase a consortium of 40 institutional members and 10 observers was formed. The Consortium with official support from five European governments applied for the ESFRI roadmap update in 2021. As announced on 30 June 2021, the ESFRI committee has selected EuPRAXIA as

one of 11 future research infrastructures with highest importance for Europe. Quoting from the ESFRI press release: “There is a **new level of ambition** to develop globally unique, complex facilities for frontier science: Einstein Telescope – highest value project ever on the Roadmap - EUR 1.900 million, and EuPRAXIA – innovative accelerator based on plasma technology - EUR 569 million.” This success illustrates the impact of WP5 coordination and outreach. The EuPRAXIA project will exploit the WP5’s results, networks, ideas and achievements.

Reference: Press Release ESFRI, 30 June 2021. <https://www.esfri.eu/latest-esfri-news/new-ris-roadmap-2021>

3.3.4 Future Strategies in “High gradient acceleration: Plasma and Laser”

In 2012 the European Strategy Preparatory Group received for the first time detailed input about the prospects and promise of plasma accelerators, a 15 page report provided by the EU-funded European Network for Novel Accelerators (EuroNNAc). The 2017 EuroNNAC report on a European strategy (31 pages). In December 2018 the network provided a short update and input to the 2020 update of European Strategy for Particle Physics. The 2020 Update for the European Strategy for Particle Physics emphasizes in particular the importance of innovation in accelerator technology, listing it as “a powerful driver for many accelerator-based fields of science and industry” with “technologies under consideration includ[ing] high-field magnets, high-temperature superconductors, plasma wakefield acceleration and other high-gradient accelerating structures” and emphasizing the need to define “deliverables for this decade [...] in a timely fashion”. In January 2021 an expert panel “High gradient acceleration: Plasma and Laser” was initiated by the Lab Director’s Group (LDG) after consultation with WP5 leadership. The expert panel exhibits large overlap with WP5/EuroNNAc such that full synergy is ensured. The panel is charged to develop a roadmap proposal for our domain, relevant for Particle Physics in Europe. The expert panel reports to the LDG which will discuss the proposed accelerator R&D roadmap with the CERN council.

The formation of the expert panel “High gradient acceleration: Plasma and Laser” is a further success for the field of advanced accelerators, a recognition of the scientific results achieved and the efforts spent to disseminate those results into the accelerator field. EuroNNAc and EAAC played an important role in this process since we started them in 2012 and 2013 with its several reports on future strategy and R&D directions.

Reference: 2012 Statement to ESPG from EuroNNAc on Plasma Acceleration, edited by R. Assmann (CERN), A. Caldwell (MPI), M. Ferrario (INFN), J. Osterhoff (DESY), T. Tajima (LMU), H. Videau (Ecole Polytechnique), <https://cds.cern.ch/record/1560093>

Reference: Final EuroNNAC2 report in the EuCARD2 project: “A European Roadmap”, published as EU deliverable report 15.6.2017, https://edms.cern.ch/ui/file/1325207/2/EuCARD2_De17-2-Final.pdf

3.4 WP6 ACCELERATOR PERFORMANCE AND CONCEPTS

3.4.1 Task 6.1 Coordination and Communication

In total, WP6 organized 27 workshops, some of which in hybrid or virtual format. These were attended by 1798 participants – or by 914 without counting co-organised events with the large FCC community. A few of the workshops were co-organized with other ARIES work packages, e.g. WP7, or with other projects, such as HIC-for-FAIR, or with the International Committee of Future Accelerators. All 5 deliverables and 7 milestones were accomplished. About 60 articles were published in peer-reviewed journals, including Reviews of Modern Physics and Physical Review Letters, in conferences proceedings, e.g. IPAC2018, IPAC2020 etc., and in the form of CERN Yellow Reports or ARIES monographs. More than 10 Newsletter articles were published to disseminate the results. Invited presentations were given at multiple venues – conferences, workshops and schools - at an average rate of at least one per month (hence of order 50 in total), at various conferences, schools and workshops, e.g. JINR 2018, Pisa 2018, Gif2019, OWL2020, Cornell CBB 2020, etc.

Collaborations with Mexico and with Japan could be reinforced through several Mexican doctoral students at CERN, with support from CONACyT, a collaboration which had originally been launched by EuCARD, and with a few month CERN visit of a graduate student from Japan, supported by SOKENDAI. Several graduate students, mostly from the Goethe University Frankfurt, contributed to organization and follow up of some of the workshop events.

Figure 25 presents some statistics for the WP6 Workshops: geographic distribution of participants, participation in the different Workshops, and fraction of female participation.

Fig. 25: Geographic distribution of participants to WP6 Workshops (top), and total and female fraction participation in the different Workshops

3.4.2 Task 6.2: Beam Quality Control in Hadron Storage Rings and Synchrotrons

Processes causing performance degradation in past, existing and planned facilities were compiled and classified. Together with their ranking, these were summarized in Deliverable Report 6.1. Numerous mitigation approaches were collected and ranked and presented in Deliverable Report 6.3 and in Milestone Reports 31 and 32.

Concerning interfacing with technologies R&D: electron lenses were among the prominent mitigations measures for beam-beam and space charge effects, discussed at APEC2018 and Mitigations 2020; HTS thin film coating is one of the possible impedance mitigation mechanisms for impedance; crystal applications and crystal/nanostructure technologies were scrutinized at the ACN2020 workshop. A planned joint event with WP17 on the interfaces of charged particle beams and advanced materials was unfortunately hindered by the covid-19 pandemic.

The main highlight of this Task has been:

Assessing performance limitations in hadron synchrotrons [D6.1], where beam loss, single-bunch instabilities, and nonlinearities figure prominently, and a review and ranking of mitigation measures [MS31, D6.3], which included Landau octupoles, bunch-by-bunch feedback, optimised tunes, and tailored slippage factor; novel techniques emerging; for impedance effects, mechanical design optimization, feedback systems, advanced coatings (HTS,...); and for space charge, a number of other mitigations, such a reducing the peak charge density. Figure 26 shows a graphical analysis of the different mitigation measures considered as they are ranked in the different laboratories, highlighting the 5 techniques that have the highest impact.

Fig. 26: Full mitigation ranking by laboratory of performance degrading mechanisms for hadron storage rings and synchrotrons

3.4.3 Task 6.3: Reliability and Availability of Particle Accelerators

Task 6.3 compiled Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Serviceability (RAMS) methods and practices at major accelerator laboratories, created an inventory, and applied a ranking. After further analysis, Task 6.3 derived the optimal RAMS characteristics for particle accelerator systems, which were reported in Deliverable 6.2, and include availability critical systems and availability model, measures to improve reliability of key subsystems, operations modelling, and fault-tolerant system design. The identified best RAMS practices were communicated to the partner institutes as well as to the entire accelerator community to advance a common RAMS baseline.

The development of an Open Data Infrastructure for accelerator reliability, including an extensive literature survey and a series of topical workshops, resulted in the architecture design and implementation of the Accelerator Reliability Information System (ARIS) as a proof of concept, documented in Milestone Report 32. The main Task highlight has been:

Defining optimal RAMS characteristics for accelerators [ARIES D6.2], covering the availability critical systems and availability model (example FCC-ee); measures to improve reliability of power converters, RF system, and electrical distribution (lead causes of unavailability for CERN’s normal conducting machines); operations modelling platform (example FCC-hh) for allocating availability goals to different sub-machines, and fault-tolerant system design. The Accelerator Reliability Information System (ARIS) was developed as a proof of concept open data infrastructure for accelerator reliability.

3.4.6 Task 6.5: Far Future Concepts & Feasibility

The objectives were met through four dedicated workshops and a final community survey. Several different muon collider options were identified and a possible R&D path forward proposed. Partly thanks to this activity, R&D on muon colliders and high gradient acceleration (including crystal acceleration) gathered support from the 2020 Strategy Update. The final overall conclusions are documented in the “White list of ranked far-future accelerator options” (D6.5). Notable highlights for this far-sighting Task have been:

Reviving and advancing the designs of a muon collider, either proton based with advanced ingredients like parametric ionization cooling, or based on positron annihilation without cooling, and helping to prepare the corresponding input to the European Strategy Update (ESU) 2019/20, which then indeed endorsed R&D on muon colliders. This will be pursued in I.FAST, through a dedicated working group and/or European R&D panel, and the US Snowmass process.

Launching pioneering discussions of using storage rings and accelerator technologies for the detection or generation of gravitational waves, which may gather significant momentum in the coming years, and already stimulated concrete plans for a first experiment in an LHC access shaft.

Developing the design, feasibility demonstration and possible operation modes for the proposed Gamma Factory based on partially stripped heavy-ion beams in the LHC colliding with suitable laser pulses, which became one of the inputs to the European Strategy Process, and is pursued through a multi-step experimental demonstration process at the CERN SPS and LHC.

Making the case for, revealing the advances of, and preparing future R&D paths for the application of bent crystals (which have now been included in the HL-LHC collimation baseline) and for crystal/nanostructure acceleration, which is an interesting and possibly more promising alternative to plasma acceleration, with potential gradients up to a factor of 1000 higher than in a plasma.

Ranking of (far-)future accelerator options [D6.5], which will serve as a future roadmap, with priority advocated for (1) energy recovery linacs, crystal bending, Gamma Factory; (2) muon collider(s), plasma & crystal & nanostr. acceleration, gravitational wave detection. These are broadly aligned with the ESU19/20 (muon colliders, plasma, energy recovery), but add the crystal bending, crystal acceleration, Gamma Factory, and the use of storage rings for gravitational wave detection.

Figure 28 presents a summary of accelerator-based detection and generation options of gravitational waves, and Table 1 shows the ranking far-future accelerator options resulting from the consultation of the ARIES community.

Fig. 28: Accelerator detection (and generation) options for gravitational waves

Table 1: white-list of ranked far-future accelerator options

Time scale	Priority and focus
10-15 years	Energy recovery Crystal bending Gamma Factory
15-30 years	Proton based muon collider Plasma acceleration Positron based muon collider Crystal and nanostructure acceleration Gravitational wave detection using storage rings
	Low or no priority
	Photon collider Crystalline beams “Moessbauer acceleration” using photon entanglement Gravitational wave generation using accelerators Non-electromagnetic acceleration or focusing mechanisms

3.5 WP7 RINGS WITH ULTRA-LOW EMITTANCE (RULE)

This Network gathered the world-leading laboratories in R&D for low emittance rings (synchrotron light facilities, damping rings for colliders, and advanced factories). It focused on the specific technical challenges that will need to be tackled for these new rings in the coming years and promoted and supported common beam tests as well as provided a platform for collaborative efforts in the commissioning of new facilities.

WP7 has supported networking activities and seven Workshops, several of which specifically dedicated to the specific aspects the design and technology of low emittance rings subsystems:

- First topical workshop on injection and injection systems for ultra-low emittance rings, Bessy-II, Berlin (Germany), August 2017.
- 7th General Low Emittance Ring network workshop, CERN, January 2018.
- Topical workshop on diagnostics for ultra-low emittance rings, Chilton (UK), April 2018.
- Topical workshop on commissioning of ultra-low emittance ring, KIT, Karlsruhe (Germany), February 2018.
- Second topical workshop on injection and injection systems for ultra-low emittance rings, TWISS, PSI, Villigen (Switzerland), February 2019.
- Advanced Low-Emittance Ring Technology (ALERT2019), with topical theme “rings with small apertures”, in Ioannina (Greece), July 2019.
- 8th General Low Emittance Ring network workshop, (virtual) INFN, Frascati, October 2020.

These workshops have been well attended, usually by ~80 delegates for the general workshop and ~40 for the topical workshop, with a notable spike to 160 delegates for the virtual workshop in October 2020.

3.5.1 Task 7.2. Injection Systems for ultra-low emittance rings

For injection schemes, WP7 has analysed and promoted schemes based on new beam physics ideas, on technological advance in the design of kickers and striplines and on the development of new pulsed power modulators. Use of new kickers with zero field on-axis (non-linear kicker, NLK) has emerged, requiring the joint development of new injection schemes.

Novel injection schemes based on on-axis injection, in many different variants, have been proposed in recent years. These developments are pushing the boundaries of existing technology of fast HV pulsers. In some cases, pulses with up to 40 kV and 2 ns 0-0 duration are foreseen, with good stability and reproducibility. This requires new technologies for fast switching (high current) devices and also new topological concept in the construction of such pulsers. In particular a modular approach whereby many fast switches operating at lower voltage (~100 V) are combined seems to be very promising and is under study at different laboratories. Figure 29 reports some examples of the measured HV fast pulses.

Figure 29: HV pulsed measured at DAFNE (left) and HEPS (right).

3.5.2 Task 7.3. Beam dynamics and technology for ultra-low emittance rings

The operation of ultra-low emittance ring is underpinned by technological advances in many key subsystems, including magnets and vacuum systems with small apertures, harmonic RF systems, advanced diagnostics which ensure the correct implementation of the nominal beam optics.

In this framework, the second topical workshop on the technology for ultra-low emittance rings (ALERT2019) has been dedicated to the technological implication of operating with small aperture high gradient magnets. The field has pushed significantly the use of permanent magnet (PM) based designs. While the ESRF-EBS has pioneered the use of PM dipole for their longitudinal gradient, a strong R&D is ongoing to extend this idea to quadrupoles, combined function dipoles and possibly higher order multipoles. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a few examples of the new concepts presented for the dipole of Spring-8 and tuneable quadrupoles for the CLIC drive beam.

Innovative magnet systems for quadrupole gradients approaching 100 T/m have been analysed and compared, allowing a reduction in the emittance by a factor of 7. Such gradients can be reached with reduced bore magnet radius to achieve the desired field quality and reduce the power consumption. As a consequence, the vacuum system should also be designed with significantly reduced apertures. These problems are tackled with the extensive use of NEG coatings of the vacuum chambers. Novel solutions have been analysed, with a notable involvement of industries.

Collective effects have been analysed, including semi-analytical characterisation of surface impedance, experimental characterisation of coating materials, and effect of harmonic cavities.

3.5.3 Task 7.4. Beam tests and commissioning of ultra-low emittance rings

WP7 has supported the experimental tests on a number of critical points for the design and operation of low emittance rings. These include joint experimental sessions taken place for a beam test and a workshop aiming to the beam tests and commissioning of LERs. Tests included beam injection and extraction, insertion devices, orbit feedbacks, low- and negative momentum compaction factors, done at several European facilities, followed by a joint measurement campaign at the three key facilities KARA, SOLEIL and SLS. A dedicated Workshop allowed exchanging experience on past and ongoing beam commissioning activities of low emittance rings. The successful commissioning of the

ESRF-EBS (Fig. 23) was based on a large preparatory effort in the so-called commissioning simulations that were presented and discussed in the topical workshops with the support of WP7.

3.6 WP14 PROMOTING INNOVATION

The innovation potential of ARIES technologies has been steered at the best by the several actions implemented within WP14. In particular, the programme included a competitive internal funding action for initiatives with industry called the “Proof-of-Concept”, and three R&D activities with industry.

3.6.1 Task 14.2 Proof of Concept Innovation Fund

The Proof-of-Concept (PoC) fund was used to demonstrate commercial viability of technologies related to the ARIES activities, selected following a competitive call after the start of the project. The innovation criteria for eligibility, selection and award of PoC fund have been discussed at Steering Committee meetings and eventually approved by the ARIES project management in autumn 2017. PoC projects had to be implemented by a minimum of two partners, one academic and the other industrial. The leading institute in the collaboration had to be a beneficiary of ARIES, to allow internal redistribution of funding to the selected projects.

The exact calendar for implementation of the PoC has been:

- September 2017: Approval by Steering Committee of Deliverable 14.1, stating criteria and management of PoC, including methodology for project selection.
- End of 2017: PoC dedicated web site is made public - the call is open, with closure in March 2018. The poster is shown in Fig. 30.
- May 2018: Assessment and Evaluation report finalized for the 10 proposals presented.
- June 2018: The Steering Committee invites to CERN the first 4 projects to present their proposals. Projects received formal awarding on June 15th.
- August 2018 - Project Coordinator notifies winners about administrative procedures.
- April 2021: the Final Reports from PoC Projects are submitted and approved.

Fig. 30: Poster to announce the Proof-of-Concept

The evaluation was carried out by an Evaluation Committee chaired by the WP Coordinator and appointed by the ARIES Industry Advisory Board (IAB). Monitoring of the projects was responsibility of WP14.

The four selected projects, each funded with 50'000 Euros, and their leading institute (member of ARIES) are:

1. Riga Technical University (RTU), “Development of an hybrid electron accelerator system for the treatment of marine diesel exhaust gas.”
2. RHP, “Investigation of new methods for the manufacturing of copper diamond composites with tailored thermo-physical properties”.
3. CEA, “Atomic layer deposition: an innovative approach for next generation particle accelerators”
4. University of Liverpool, “Accelerator Diagnostic using innovative Adaptive Optics”.

The 4 PoC projects have each produced specific technical results that are detailed below. The PoC exercise, first of the kind in a EC funded project for accelerators, has demonstrated to be effective in helping and supporting innovative ideas and in attracting additional resources from academic institutions, funding agencies, and industries.

Achievements of the PoC projects

- **PoC Project: “Development of a hybrid electron accelerator system for the treatment of marine diesel exhaust gas.”. Project leader: Riga Technical University**

The main objective of this PoC was the demonstration in field condition of a new technology for removing dangerous pollutants from the exhaust gases of ship diesel engines. The system is designed in such way that it could be used to retrofit existing ships with a pollution-reduction technology. It includes a small particle accelerator for electrons at 50-100 keV energy applied to the exhausts of the

diesel engine to break the chemical bounds of high-order pollutant oxides SO_x and NO_x and of particulate matter, to ease the final removal of the pollutants in a small conventional scrubber – a device to remove molecules from the gas using a water jet.

For this purpose, a dedicated experiment has been set-up in the Riga Shipyard, using as test bench a tugboat moored at the yard and a movable accelerator usually employed for the sterilization of seeds, as shown in Figures 31 and 32. With limited time for tests and limited financial resources, the experiment proved that the technology is possible and obtained valuable technical input for future collaborations. The PoC has been instrumental into mobilizing resources and interests from different actors, which have materialized into the submission of a H2020 proposal (HERTIS). The pilot project demonstrated that particle accelerators can be successfully deployed in the maritime conditions; an economic feasibility analysis supported within the PoC indicated the profitability of this technology when compared to using catalytic systems and low-Sulphur fuels. More specifically, the experiment has confirmed, with accurate measurements, that with low-energy and non-homogeneous electron irradiation dose (penetration level) provided by the movable accelerators and using a standard wet-scrubber hybrid system, NO_x reduction at full engine load reached 45%. Removal of Sulphur could not be measured because of the ban on using high-Sulphur fuel in port, but all indicators agreed that a comparably high removal rate was indeed in reach. The consortium is confident that using a higher, homogenous irradiation dose, SO_x, NO_x and particulate removal efficiency can reach the target values. A patent has been submitted. Should be underlined that the ARIES funding acted as a seed to catalyze substantial contributions by the partners, both in-kind and cash.

Figure 31: The tug boat and its exhaust connected to Fraunhofer accelerator.

Figure 32: The team at Riga shipyard for the experiment data taking in April 2019.

- **PoC project: “Investigation of new methods for the manufacturing of copper diamond composites with tailored thermo-physical properties”. Project leader: RHP**

The project objective was, by using Plasma Metal Deposition processes (PMD), to manufacture metal diamond composites that at the same time present a high thermal conductivity (K_t) and a low coefficient of thermal expansion. This material could be properly applied in many front-edge applications, for example in Collimators. PMD processes allow building large components or more complex geometries using a layer by layer approach. One approach investigated during this reporting

period was to manufacture small scale samples where pre-compacted feedstocks combined with a fast-thermal process are combined. In this way, samples of K_t of around 350 - 400 W/mK have been realized. Some open issues still to solve are the remaining porosities linked to process optimization and eventually the upscaling of the process in view of industrial applications and commercialization. For this last point, a very high degree of process control and therefore the setup of a dedicated manufacturing system will be necessary.

- **PoC project: “Atomic layer deposition: an innovative approach for next generation particle accelerators”. Project leader: CEA**

The project objective was to develop new materials and structures able to improve performances of Particle Accelerator components and of SRF cavities by using Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) technique. The project has developed a methodology for improving SRF cavity performance on coupon sample before and to apply it to a scale cavity later when the main parameters are validated. ALD can develop thin films of hetero-structures that can be synthesized in a conformal and controlled manner on almost any substrates materials and geometry. ALD compared to usual deposition techniques, can be easily scalable to large objects and for industrial production once the “recipes” have been optimized on coupons and bench scale. In P2, the PoC project has allowed the preparation of ALD set-up and has produced promising results on coupon samples.

- **PoC project: “Accelerator Diagnostic using Innovative Adaptive Optics”. Project leader: University of Liverpool**

The InnoAdO project objective was to design, build and test a Prototype optical DMD (digital micromirror device) interferometry (ODI) and optical phase space mapping (OPSM) systems. The prototype optical DMD and OPMS systems have produced a comprehensive set of measurements demonstrating the validity of the prototype. Simulation studies have been supporting the prototyping activities.

All the projects have gathered a wide interest in their respective communities and have attracted considerable amount of internal resources to supplement the EC contribution from ARIES. The societal impact of these project is evident not only in the flagship project aimed at reducing pollution from shipping, but also in the R&D for X-sources instrumentation and diagnostics, crucial at a time when synchrotron light sources are used to analyse the diffraction patterns of the COVID-19 virus.

3.6.2 Task 14.3 Collaboration with industry

This Task aimed at increasing synergies between laboratories, universities, specialized institutes and applied research institutes. Its main strategic tool was the ARIES Industry Advisory Board (IAB), a body composed of 5 industry members mandated for advising the ARIES Project on matters relating with industrial collaborations and for the managing of the Proof-of-Concept fund. Some specific technical and organizational subjects to foster participation of industry in accelerator projects were addressed in a series of Workshops and events organized by Task 14.3:

- the Accelerator-Industry Co-Innovation Workshop - Tools and strategies to enhance industry-academia cooperation in the particle accelerator community, which took place at Brussels on February 6 and 7 and was organized jointly with the TIARA Collaboration and the AMICI EU project.

- A workshop in CERN, on Dec 1, 2017, organized in cooperation among WP3 and WP14, on electron-beam application for diesel motor exhaust gas purification.
- A workshop organized with the AMICI EU-project at CERN, on May 16th 2018, with the title “ AMICI-ARIES workshop on Intellectual Property in collaborating activities between Research and Technical Infrastructure and Industry”. Key IPR experts from 4 EU laboratories participated, to address the problematic of IPR in collaborations.
- An industry-academia event organized in Budapest, on March 8th 2019, with participation of about 40 experts from EU laboratories and industries on Additive Manufacturing.
- A second industry-academia event that had to be organized virtually in June 2021 because of the Covid emergency was devoted to RAMI (Reliability, Availability, Maintainability, and Inspectability), co-organised by STFC, CERN, and Wigner institute.

3.6.3 Task 14.3 Industrial production of materials for extreme thermal management

The Task has been producing in industry prototype samples of composite materials for extreme thermal management, an essential requirement for accelerator collimators and targets that is shared by several industrial applications. The material produced aimed at combining properties of graphite or diamond (low ρ , high λ , low α) with those of metal and transition metal-based ceramics (high R_m , good γ). Thermal analysis of the prototype samples was carried out in WP17. Additional materials considered were Silver-diamond (AgCD), Copper-diamond (CuCD), Molybdenum-graphite (MoGr). The samples made of ceramic-graphite and copper-diamond were all produced and characterized well in advance of schedule, to coordinate the technical development with WP17. The produced samples are shown in Figure 33.

Fig. 33: Material samples produced by industry for Task 14.4

The samples were produced by industries (RHP and Brevetti Bizz) in shapes required by testing devices, and with quality in excess of the specifications, using advanced techniques: Spark-Plasma-

Sintering and Additive Manufacturing. The material characterization performed in WP17 has resulted in properties above the original target in particular for the critical value of thermal conductivity.

An additional result within this Task was the development in the participating industry of a procedure for deposition of the superconducting material MgB₂ on metal substrate, an objective beyond the initial scope of the Task made possible by the availability of infrastructure and competences in the company and by some minor redistribution of resources within the ARIES project. After several attempts, a viable industrial process has been defined, able to produce layers of MgB₂ showing proper microstructures and good superconductive properties. Figure 34 shows the measured superconducting properties of the final batch of samples.

Fig. 34: final superconducting properties of MgB₂ samples

3.6.4 Task 14.5 HTS cable development for accelerator magnets

The goal of this Task was the manufacture of HTS (High-Temperature Superconducting) coated conductor depositing REBCO (Rare-Earth Barium Copper Oxide) on a 50 μm thick substrate. The use of such thin stainless-steel tape is an absolute novelty in the panorama of coated conductor.

The industrial partner, Bruker HTS GmbH (BHTS) adapted the equipment and the process and obtained tapes with record current density, beyond the ARIES goal. An unexpected issue (a bi-directional bending) has adversely affected the process that had to be adjusted to mitigate the effect, causing a reduction of the critical current of 30%. Nevertheless, the maximum measured engineering current density J_e of 1150 A/mm² at 4.2 K, 19 T, 90° is still exceeding the goal of ARIES that was to achieve over > 100 m of conductor a value > 800A/mm² at 4.2K, 18 T. The measured engineering current density is shown in Figure 35, for a standard cable sample, and for the record one.

Fig. 35: Measured engineering current density as function of magnetic field for two samples tapes, Q065-18 and Q064-18.

In total 413 m of HTS tape of 12 mm width and 50 μm substrate thickness have been produced using a specially developed process:

1. Preparation of stainless-steel tape substrate (with surface smoothness at few nm level). Any defect in this phase is assumed as a potential reason for a fatal defect of conductor performance.
2. Deposition of thick film of ceramic buffer layer for texturing made of Yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), via ABAD (alternating ion beam assisted deposition) at ambient temperature. ABAD is a proprietary process of BHTS. The YSZ is about 2-3 μm thick.
3. Deposition of REBCO (RE= yttrium in our case) by PLD technology, a process carried out at high temperature. BHTS utilizes Yttrium as rare earth. The YBCO film is about 2 μm thick.
4. Coating with a few μm of silver to protect the superconducting layer (typically 1 μm on the backside and 2-4 μm on the functional side (YBCO side).
5. Coating with 2x20 μm (or other thickness) of copper for final stabilization.

3.6.5 Task 14.6 Accelerator timing system

The Central Timing System (CTS) is a distributed and scalable system for synchronising the operation of numerous devices distributed across the accelerator (beam diagnostic, power supplies, i/o digital....). While the CTS is usually custom-made in the different accelerator laboratories, the goal of ARIES Task 14.6 was to start from a specific CTS system called “RedNET” (Realtime Event Distribution Network) developed in the past by CERN and the industrial partner Cosylab for the MedAustron medical accelerator project, to upgrade and customise it to become a generalised system deployable on a large number of small accelerators, including those subjects to medical operation requirements.

The co-developed new architecture and design is made available in Open Access format under the H2020 rules as a cooperative effort of CERN and Cosylab. The developments in the scope of ARIES form the baseline for the development of the system subject to a dedicated contract between ADAM S.A. (Meyrin, Geneva) and Cosylab. ADAM S.A. has adopted the ARIES development for the design and construction of a novel linear accelerator for image-guided cancer therapy with protons. The Open Access “RedNET” is now part of the Cosylab general accelerator control package under the name C-MTS. Prospected customers are small to medium sized particle accelerators for medical and industrial applications. A content page added to the website of Cosylab (Figure 36) promotes the product and present the results of the action in the frame of ARIES, acknowledging the ARIES and EC contribution.

Fig. 36: Cosylab web page advertising the C-MTS with RedNET functionalities, and acknowledgements

3.7 WP15 THIN FILMS FOR SUPERCONDUCTING RF CAVITIES

The WP15 objective was to test and improve different superconducting coatings (Nb, Nb₃Sn, NbN, NbTiN, *etc.* on Copper substrate) to enable achieving quality factor and surface resistance equal or higher than bulk Nb and increase of RF critical field. The emphasis was made on better understanding of a correlation between substrate preparation, thin film deposition process and characterisation, the DC and AC SC evaluation results and, finally, the behaviour at the RF conditions.

3.7.1 Task 15.2. Substrate surface preparation

The objective for this task was optimising cleaning and polishing procedure for surface preparation for Cu substrate for Nb coating minimising the substrate effect on the final film properties.

50 planar copper samples with a size of 53 mm x 53 mm were cut at CERN from the same copper sheet then polished with different procedures. Based on results from 1st and 2nd year SUBU-type chemical polishing and electro-polishing were selected as most promising procedures for the following WP15 work. These techniques were applied to the quadrupole resonators (QPR) samples prior the thin film deposition.

The results were presented in IPAC and SRF conferences, and at the International Workshops on Thin Films & New Ideas for Pushing the Limits of RF Superconductivity.

3.7.2 Task 15.3. Thin film deposition and analysis

The main focus of this task was on development deposition techniques and characterisation of non-Nb superconducting thin films:

- System 1 - Nb₃Sn, System 2 - NbN, System 3 - NbTiN,
- SIS and SS systems (superconductor-insulator-superconductor) multilayer coatings,

with evaluation of the AC/DC superconducting properties for all the tested samples. These knowledge and experience were applied for coating of the quadrupole resonators (QPR) samples.

Additionally, was explored a laser treatment of Cu substrates and Nb films. Figure 37 shows the deposition facilities used at different ARIES laboratories.

Fig. 37: ARIES deposition facilities at U. Siegen, LNL/INFN, and ASTeC/STFC

The main results of the Nb film irradiated by laser were that the sizes of Nb crystals can be increased, defects between grains (pinholes) can be eliminated, and superconducting properties are changing. Figure 38 shows SEM images of Nb/Cu structure before and after irradiation.

Fig. 38: SEM images of Nb/Cu structure before irradiation (a) and after irradiation by Nd:YAG laser with $I_1 = 140 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (b); $I_2 = 170 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (c); $I_3 = 253 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (d); $I_4 = 320 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (e).

The results are reported in Deliverable Reports 15.3 and 15.4 and have been presented in 6 talks at the 9th International Workshop on Thin Films & New Ideas for Pushing the Limits of RF Superconductivity, 15-18 March 2021. The further progress with these activities has been reported in at the SRF-2021 conference, 28th June – 2nd July 2021.

3.7.3 Task 15.4. Superconductivity evaluation

The Task main objective was the DC and RF testing of the superconducting thin films produced by the partners. These measurements were performed at several laboratories, and extensively reported in the final Deliverable Report D15.4 that is covering the activities over 12 months (M37-M48) and is also highlighting the main results achieved within four years of ARIES.

A magnetic field penetration facility (based on a novel idea for testing candidate thin films for SRF cavities) has been built, tested and applied for sample characterisation.

Figure 39 shows a graphical analysis of the progress made with preparation testing of 5 QPR samples between different ARIES partners. The table corresponds to the situation in early 2021, and all testing have been completed by June 2021 and being analysed in present.

Samp							
B-1	SUBU	3 μm Nb film	Cutting, Stripping, EP	3 μm Nb film	Laser treatment	Field Penetration	
B-2	SUBU	2 μm Nb film	RF test	Recoat.: 7.3 μm Nb	RF test	RF test	Stripping, SUBU, INFN Nb
B-3	EP	3 μm Nb film	RF test	SIS: 3 μm Nb/30 nm AlN/100 nm NbN	RF test	Stripping, SUBU, INFN	TBD
B-4	EP	3 μm Nb film	RF test	Stripping, INFN EP	SIS	RF test	Stripping, INFN EP
B-5	SUBU	3 μm Nb film	RF test	Laser treatment	RF test	Stripping, SUBU, INFN	SIS

DONE

 IN PROCESS

 FAILED

Fig. 39: preparation and testing workflow for 5 samples

4. Potential impact (on science and/or society for entire project)

4.1 WP3 INDUSTRIAL AND SOCIETAL APPLICATIONS

The WP3 has the potential to have a larger than expected industrial and societal impact. Some examples of this are as follows.

1. The global marine production of SO₂ and NO_x are due to exceed the land production by the early 2020s and the only current potential solution able to deal with both of these, plus other organic contaminants, is the use of electron beams. The project to study this process and a novel accelerator solution is making good progress and tests are planned on board a ship soon.
2. Work is underway on the use of electron beams to treat sewage sludge. As well as increasing the efficiency for biogas production and making clearer, more valuable fertiliser, this can also deal with the increase in anti-microbial resistance (AMR) from the treatment. This is a major world-wide concern. As well as destroying the bacteria and viruses, electron beams may also be able to break up the antibiotics themselves. The accelerators could be used at either the treatment plant or at the major sources of the bacteria and antibiotics, hospitals and pharmaceutical companies. Electron beams also have the potential to destroy other contaminants in sludge, including other pharmaceuticals and personal care products and persistent organic pollutants. They may also enable the removal of microplastics. Their advantage over other existing techniques is they do all these things at the same time without the addition of chemicals. A “zero energy” plant for municipal waste sludge treatment with electron accelerator which provides electricity to supply accelerator and other equipment and producing safe organic fertilizer is under construction.
3. Besides delivering high doses to kill pathogens, automated LEEI also abolished proliferation of the human NK cell line NK-92, through the application of a much lower dose. The cell line is used in clinical trials for cancer therapy, and must be rendered proliferation-deficient before being applied to patients. This is performed through irradiation with 10 Gy. At the same time, the cells need to maintain their cytotoxic anti-cancer cell activity over several days. This indicates that LEEI could also be used in the generation of cell therapeutic strategies. Currently licensed cell therapies consist of autologous immune cells, and are therefore complex and expensive in manufacturing. The usage of cell lines would have clear advantages, as these would enable off-the-shelf products, provided that the cells are proliferation-incompetent. A detailed comparison of LEEI and the currently used gamma- or X-rays in immune cell irradiation still needs to be performed, but first results show at least equal performances of LEEI-inactivated and state-of-the art irradiated NK-cells.
4. The numerous studies demonstrating that ionizing irradiation is a promising technology for the generation of inactivated vaccines were confirmed by the LEEI-inactivated RSV. There is a particular demand for alternative inactivation methods for RSV, as the usage of

formaldehyde has been associated with an enhanced course of the disease after subsequent natural infection.

5. For radiotherapy, many challenges, both technological and biological, have to be addressed and overcome for the ultimate goal of using VHEE and VHEE-FLASH as an innovative modality for effective cancer treatment with minimal damage to healthy tissues. From the accelerator technology point of view an important point is to assess the possibility of focusing and scanning transversely the beam, thereby overcoming the disadvantages associated in the past with low energy electron and photon beam irradiation. Stability, reliability and repeatability are other mandatory ingredients for accelerators to be operated in a medical environment.

The major challenge for VHEE-FLASH is the delivery of very high dose-rate, possibly over a large area, providing a uniform dose distribution throughout the target. Also the parameter window in which the FLASH effect takes place has still to be thoroughly defined, as well as its effectiveness as a function of the physical parameters of the electron beam. This, together with a clear understanding of the underlying biological processes will likely prove to be essential in order to fully optimize the FLASH RT technique. Finally, of particular importance, is the development of reliable on-line dosimetry for very high dose rates, a regime not adapted to the current standard dosimetry techniques for RT. Ionization chambers, routinely used in medical linacs, suffer from nonlinear effects at very high dose rates, and in order to get reliable measurements R&D is needed to develop novel ion chamber types, or explore alternative possibilities as solid state detectors or the use of calibrated beam diagnostics.

All this asks for a large beam test activity, in order to experimentally characterize VHEE beams and their ability to produce the FLASH effect, and provide a test bed for the associated technologies. Besides an important R&D accelerator technology effort in conventional, mainly RF linacs, and advance accelerator technologies, as laser-plasma, has to be developed to go further in the quest for compact and efficient VHEE RT in the range of hundred MeV. For achieving these aims, a synergistic and multidisciplinary research effort based on accelerator technology as well as physical and radiobiological comparisons to see how well VHEE can meet the current assumptions and become a clinical reality is needed. In this framework the ARIES project and in particular the WP3 has been the perfect catalyser to initiate and consolidate the R&D accelerator technology aspects.

6. The activities performed in task 3.5 have had a strong impact in the main challenges of the current radioisotope supply market. The better understanding of the physical phenomena during beam acceleration allows the optimization of the radioisotope production through a careful choice of the beam energy and current, with minimum impact on the machine footprint and activation. The maintenance tasks are minimized by controlling the beam losses, improving the ion source behaviour and reducing the dependence on external cryogenics. Special important is the reduction of the running costs with the development of efficient cooling systems.

4.2 WP4 EFFICIENT ENERGY MANAGEMENT

WP4 had a strong impact in structuring the accelerator community towards finding common solutions to the energy problem of large accelerator-based research infrastructures. In particular, the WP has produced the following technical results:

- Development of the design of a new 12 GHz high efficiency klystron radio-frequency power supply (called “kladistron”) with 65% efficiency that can be used for future compact FEL light sources.
- a new concept for the target and moderator geometry optimization of the SINQ facility at PSI, leading to substantial energy saving.
- much improved understanding of magnetic shielding against flux trapping in superconducting RF cavities.
- Development of a prototype pulsed quadrupole power supply equipped with a specially-designed circuit recovering 28% of the energy from pulse to pulse.

4.3 WP5 EUROPEAN NETWORK FOR NOVEL ACCELERATORS

The estimated potential impacts from WP5 have developed into real, measurable impacts through a new European project EuPRAXIA, that will bring shorter term benefits of our new technologies to science and society. EuPRAXIA has been placed on the 2021 update of the ESFRI roadmap and has already received funding in excess of 120 M€ from various sources in particular the Italian government. The explicit inclusion of the WP5 theme into the European strategy for Particle Physics aims at longer term impacts that are now being evaluated together with Particle Physics in Europe.

4.4 WP6 ACCELERATOR PERFORMANCE AND CONCEPTS

The potential impact of ARIES WP6 on accelerators is significant. WP6 APEC has set the foundations for defining new directions in accelerator science. The network activities have focused the attention of the community on certain key aspects, which will allow designing future accelerators for new discoveries, while optimizing existing ones. In particular, APEC has sparked an interest in using storage rings and accelerator technologies for gravitational-wave research, and it advanced several studies on the high-precision operation of accelerators and beam diagnostics.

A more direct benefit to society derives from the ARIES efforts on controlling the beam delivery and rendering accelerator operation highly reliable. The pertinent methodologies will eventually be transferred to all types of accelerator applications, and they will help to produce well-tailored beams for many users, including for industrial and medical applications.

4.5 WP7 RINGS WITH ULTRA-LOW EMITTANCE

The ARIES WP7 has created a solid network between the laboratories engaged in the desing, construction and operation of ultra-low emittance ring for light sources and colliders, in EU and beyond. The general workshops have provided extensive overviews of the most recent advances in

the field and have stimulated both new developments in the concept of multi-bend achromatic and open exchange of ideas and collaborations. The topical workshops have created the framework for in-depth technical discussion of specific issues, mostly related to new hardware development, such as magnets, fast pulsers and kickers and small aperture vacuum chambers. Industrial partners have been actively participating to these workshops. Three facilities using MBA lattices are now in operation around the world (ESRF-EBS and MAX IV in Europe) and virtually all existing laboratories are proposing upgrade programmes for the next 5-10 years.

The societal impact of these activities resides in the support for the development of these new type of accelerators, whose extremely bright beams will open up new research routes with applications in physics, chemistry, biology.

4.6 WP14 PROMOTING INNOVATION

The contribution of WP14 to the expected impact has been fully met. A part the several scientific objectives, all reached and exceeded, the WP14 has validated a way of effective collaboration between industry and laboratories, mainly via the tasks 14.3,14.4,14.5. Moreover, with the success of the PoC scheme, it has been increased the level of innovation and Technology Transfer from accelerator science to the benefit of societal applications.

4.7 WP15 THIN FILMS FOR SUPERCONDUCTING RF CAVITIES

The ARIES WP15 team achieved all of its goals, the Milestones and Deliverables have been successfully achieved. The team progressed with better understanding of an impact of the Cu substrate polishing and impact of various polishing techniques on a quality of superconducting films. The SC film deposition process has been developed for producing various superconducting thin films characterisation. The collaboration effort results in better understanding of a correlation between substrate preparation, deposition process, thin film characteristic, the DC and AC SC evaluation results and the TF behaviour at the RF conditions.

The knowledge and experience obtained by WP partners in copper substrate preparation and deposition of non-Nb TF materials with higher T_c are enabling progressing to the next stage: developing a real cavity prototype coated with non-Nb superconducting TF and SIS structures. The potential benefit of this should be increasing of Q_0 and E characteristics, a possibility of operation for SRF cavities at 4 K instead of 1.8 K leading to reducing the initial and operation costs the RF systems. In the follow-up project within H2020 I.FAST WP9, all this will be initially applied to 6 and 3 GHz copper cavities for developing a 3D coating technology, then it should be demonstrated with a 1.3-GHz copper cavity which should be deposited with non-Nb SC TF (including SIS structures) and fully tested with a RF power.

5. list of exploitable foreground for entire project

WP	Type of exploitation foreground ⁵	Description of exploitable foreground (relevant deliverable)	Purpose (How the foreground might be exploited and by whom)	IPR ⁶	Potential/expected impact (quantify where possible)	Exploitable product(s) or measure(s)	Sector(s) of application	Timetable, commercial or any other use
3	INV	“Zero-energy technology for the manufacturing of biologically safe organic fertilizers based on sewage sludge”	Being implemented by Consortium Biopolinex SA (leader) and INCT (R&D)	open	Decontamination of municipal sewage and the production of an organic fertilizer useful for agricultural purposes. Action imposed by EU Directive.	Project granted by National Center for Research and Development, Poland POIR.04.01.04-00-0078/17	Municipal wastewater treatment plants	Year of demo plant construction 2023
3	INV	"Design and verification on a pilot scale of a system for collection and	To be implemented by Remontowa Shipyard SA, Gdańsk, Poland on basis of R@D developed by INCT	industrial know how	Elimination of the risks associated with ballast water	Sector Program 8 Innovation Pilot Proposal Form	Shipyards and ports following	Year of implementation 2024

		treatment of ballast water and sludge from the ship and technological waters from the ship hull cleaning process, using ionizing radiation for the utilization of pollutants”			contamination and re-use of the water after previous decontamination. Action imposed by maritime standards	INNOship Project POIR.01.02.00-00-0007/18		
3	INV	A method of cleaning exhaust gases emitted by diesel engines, in particular, installed at sea transport vessels	Further activities were related to HERTIS project preparation. The application for EU projects is foreseen.	Patent application	Elimination of SO2 and NOx from exhaust gases emitted by diesel engines installed at sea transport vessels	Polish patent application P. 435454	Ship industry	Consortium agreed on “on board” pilot testing – the financing is searched for.
4	GAK	Characterisation Method for Nb samples	Institutions engaged in s.c, RF	Invention	Faster and cost efficient R&D cycles of s.c, RF	Device to do measurements	Particle accelerators	
4		New technology for energy efficient beam transport systems	Companies producing accelerator components	Invention	Low investment cost, low operation cost and energy efficient	High current pulsed magnets with energy recovery	Particle accelerators	

5	Other Projects	New European Research Infrastructure EuPRAXIA. See: Assmann, R.W., Weikum, M.K., Akhter, T. et al. EuPRAXIA Conceptual Design Report. Eur. Phys. J. Spec. Top. 229, 3675–4284 (2020).	World-wide first user facility based on plasma technology, user beamlines for various science fields and medical applications, development platform for technologies for Europe and European industry		Calculated cost benefit return rate of 9.22% Future facilities with reduced size and cost	Beams of electrons, positrons and photons of various qualities (incl FEL) New laser technology	Accelerators, lasers, medical X rays, FEL user science, positron-based technologies	TDR until 2026. Start of operation in 2029.
6	GAK, EUP, SIN	Improved Reliability and Availability of Particle Accelerators	Exploited, applied and pursued for improving accelerator operation, and in the design of future accelerators; shared use of ARIS system	N/A	Enhanced availability and reliability of future colliders, medical accelerators, light sources, and accelerator-driven systems	Report; reliability models, newly cross-linked communities, ARIS PoC	HEP accelerators, ADS, photon sciences, nuclear science, medical accelerators	Short & medium, 0-10 years
6	GAK, EUP	Revival and advanced designs of muon colliders	Exploited and pursued in IFAST, and in parallel by the European Accelerator Expert Panels set up by CERN Council and LDG, by the EPS-AG strategy discussions, and by the US Snowmass process	N/A	So far: Muon collider R&D supported by ESU 2020; muon collider design study launched; test facilities under discussion; Future: work towards CDR.	Dedicated workshop and deliverable, reports	Particle Physics, HEP Accelerators	Short & medium, CDR in 5 years

6	GAK, SIN	ERL R&D guidelines	Exploited and pursued in IFAST, and by the European Accelerator Expert Panels set up by CERN Council and LDG, and, finally, the PERLE project	N/A	Realization of test facility PERLE; higher current ERLs	Report and database	Particle Physics, nuclear physics	Short & medium, within 5 years
6	GAK, EUP	Possibility of detecting gravitational waves at storage rings or using accelerator technologies	Exploited and pursued in IFAST, and by the AEON/AEDGE collaboration developing an experiment based on the LHC infrastructure	N/A	“Accelerator experiments” on novel ways to detect gravitational waves and over extended frequency scales; newly formed collaboratiосn across communities	Reports	Gravitational wave physics, accelerators, particle physics	Short & medium & long, 0-30 years
6	GAK, EUP, SIN	“Gamma Factory” option	Exploited and pursued by the PBC effort at CERN, with staged beam experiments at the SPS and LHC	N/A	Gamma factory based on partially stripped heavy ion beams in the LHC, with numerous applications	Reports	Particle physics, nuclear physics, material sciences	Medium, 5-10 years
6	GAK, EUP	Novel options for extremely high-gradient acceleration: crystals and nanostructures	Exploited and pursued in IFAST, in the US Snowmass process, and by a global collaboration	N/A	Ultracomoact accelerators with accelerating gradients above 1 TV/m	Reports	All types of accelerator applications, incl. medical accelerators	Long, 15-30 years

**TECHNICAL REPORT ON WORK PACKAGES COMPLETED AT M48
AND SUMMARY OF TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS AT M48**

Deliverable : D.1.3

Date: 01.09.2021

14	technology	industrial process definition to produce thin tapes for cable (14.5)	Superconductor cable production		Next generation of accelerators systems Next generation ion therapy gantry	HTS cable with higher performance	Magnet technology	In 5 years, for high current application (HEP, Medical, Energy)
14	technology	industrial process using e-beam accelerators (14.3)	Removal of pollutant from exhaust diesel motor		Sea-transport compliant with strict international regulations on emission		Accelerator technology	
15.2	GAK	QPR sample copper polishing	Removing a previously deposited film and copper polishing procedures on copper surface of QPR sample	Disclosure	Define a standard procedure for the copper substrates in SRF applications	Removing a previously deposited film and copper polishing protocol	SRF	Aug 2020
15.3	GAK	SIS coating with Niobium nitride (NbN) coating	Synthesis of high quality, superconducting phase stable NbN	Disclosure	Using NbN as new single layer or in SIS-structures top layer SRF material	NbN thin film protocol	SRF	Mid 2021
15.3	GAK	SIS coating with Nb ₃ Sn deposition	Synthesis of high quality	Disclosure	Using Nb ₃ Sn as new single layer or in SIS-structures	Nb ₃ Sn thin film protocol	SRF	End 2020

			superconducting Nb3Sn		top layer SRF material			
15.3	GAK	SIS coating with NbTiN deposition	Synthesis of high quality superconducting NbTiN	Disclosure	Using NbTiN as new single layer or in SIS-structures top layer SRF material	NbTiN thin film protocol	SRF	End 2020
15.3	GAK	Laser polishing	Post-deposition film engineering: grain size, density of dislocations and surface roughness	Disclosure	Change (improving) of thin film properties	Grain size, density of dislocations, surface roughness	SRF and other thin film application	Mid 2021
15.4	GAK	Planar field penetration	Characterisation of planar superconducting materials (films) with a local DC magnetic field parallel to the surface	Disclosure	A new characterisation method in SRF applications	Measurements of magnetic field penetration	SRF and other superconducting thin films	End 2020

6. Dissemination and exploitation of results

6.1 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

WP3	
N°	Author(s), Title, References, Date, Link
1	Siwek, M. & Edgecock, T, Application of electron beam water radiolysis for sewage sludge treatment: a review , Environmental Science and Pollution Research , 27, 34, p. 42424-42448 25 p., 1 Dec 2020
WP4	
N°	Author(s), Title, References, Date, Link
1	R. M. Bergmann, U. Filges, D. Kiselev, C. Klauser, E. Rantsiou, V. Talanov, M. Wohlmuther und M. Yamada, „Simulation Methods and Results of the SINQ ColdNeutron Source Upgrade Study,“ <i>Journal of Physics</i> (2018).
2	Hamel P., Plouin J., Marchand C. and Peauger F., Klystron efficiency optimization based on a genetic algorithm. 2019 International Vacuum Electronics Conference (IVEC) 1–2 (2019).
3	A. Ivanov, T. Koettig, A. Macpherson, Partial Meissner effect measurement by a superconducting magnetic flux lens, submitted to PRAB on 11 March 2021
WP5	
	A. Cianchi et al, “Proceedings of the 4 th European Advanced Accelerator Concepts Workshop 15-20 September 2019, Isola d'Elba, Italy. IOP Volume 1596 (2020).”
WP6	
	S. Casalbuoni, A.-S. Müller, F. Zimmermann (eds.), Beam Tests and Commissioning of Low Emittance Rings: Proceedings ARIES-ICFA Mini-Workshop, ARIES Monograph vol. 54 (2020)
	R. Cimino, G. Rumolo, F. Zimmermann (eds.), Proceedings “ECLLOUD’18: Joint INFN-CERN-ARIES Workshop on Electron-Cloud Effects”, CERN Yellow Report (2020)
	L. Bandiera et al., “ Summary of ARIES Workshop "Applications of Crystals and Nanotubes for Acceleration and Manipulation - ACN2020" ”, 31 March 2020
	J. Keintzel, R. Tomás, R. Bruce, M. Giovannozzi, T. Risselada, and F. Zimmermann, „Lattice and optics options for possible energy upgrades of the Large Hadron Collider,“ Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 23, 101602 (2020) https://journals.aps.org/prab/pdf/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.101602

	F. Zimmermann, et al, " Summary and Highlights of "Mitigation Approaches for Hadron Storage Rings and Synchrotrons" ", 13 November 2020
	Arto Niemi, Jussi-Pekka Penttinen, Availability and critical systems of the Future Circular Electron-Positron Collider, Nucl. Instr. Meth. A vol. 96321 (2020)
	E. Métral and M. Migliorati, "Longitudinal and transverse mode coupling instability: Vlasov solvers and tracking codes", Physical Review Accelerators and Beams 23, 071001 (2020); https://journals.aps.org/prab/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.071001
	N. Biancacci, E. Métral and M. Migliorati, "Fast-slow mode coupling instability for coasting beams in the presence of detuning impedance," Physical Review Accelerators and Beams 23, 124402 (2020); https://journals.aps.org/prab/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.124402
	M Varasteh, R. Bruce, F. Cerutti, M. Crouch, and F. Zimmermann, "Impact of betatron collimation losses in the High-Energy Large Hadron Collider," Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 24, 04160 (2021); https://journals.aps.org/prab/pdf/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.24.041601
	M. A. Valdivia Garcia and F. Zimmermann, "Beam blow up due to Beamstrahlung in circular e+e- colliders," The European Physical Journal Plus volume 136, Article number: 501 (2021); https://link.springer.com/article/10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-01485-x
	A. Berlin et al., " Storage Rings and Gravitational Waves: Summary and Outlook ," 4 May 2021
	V. Shiltsev and F. Zimmermann, "Modern and future colliders," Rev. Mod. Phys. 93, 015006 (2021) – RMP link: https://journals.aps.org/rmp/abstract/10.1103/RevModPhys.93.015006
	G. Franchetti, F. Zimmermann, and M. A. Rehman, "Trapping of neutral molecules by the beam electromagnetic field," Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 24, 054001 – PRAB link: https://journals.aps.org/prab/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.24.054001
	Z. Nergiz, N.S. Mirian, A. Aksoy, D. Zhou, F. Zimmermann, H. Aksakal, <i>Bright Angstrom and Picometre Free Electron Laser Based on the LHeC Energy Recovery Linac</i> , to be resubmitted to PRAB and/or posted on zenodo
WP14	
	Lucio Rossi and Carmine Senatore, <i>HTS Accelerator Magnet and Conductor Development in Europe, Instruments</i> 2021 , 5, 8. , (p.33) open access https://doi.org/10.3390/instruments5010008
WP15	
1	Pira, C., et al., "Impact of the Cu substrate surface preparation on the morphological, superconductive and RF properties of the Nb superconductive coatings", in Proc. SRF 2019, Dresden, Germany, 2019.
2	Turner, D., et al., "Characterization of flat multilayer thin film superconductors", in Proc. SRF 2019, Dresden, Germany, 2019.
3	Malyshev, O.B., et al. The SRF thin film test facility in LHe-free cryostat. in Proc. SRF 2019, Dresden, Germany, 2019.
4	Tikhonov, D., et al., "Superconducting thin films characterization at HZB with the quadrupole resonator", in Proc. SRF 2019, Dresden, Germany, 2019.
5	Leith, S.B., et al., "Initial results from investigations into different surface preparation techniques of OFHC copper for SRF applications", in Proc. SRF 2019, Dresden, Germany, 2019.
6	Leith, S., et al., "Deposition parameter effects on niobium nitride (NbN) thin film deposited onto copper substrates with DC magnetron sputtering", in Proc. SRF 2019, Dresden, Germany, 2019.

7	Valizadeh, R., et al., "PVD deposition of Nb ₃ Sn thin film on copper substrate from an alloy Nb ₃ Sn target", in Proc. IPAC 2019. 2019: Melbourne, Australia.
8	Ries R., et al, "Superconducting properties and surface roughness of thin Nb samples fabricated for SRF applications", J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 1559, 012040 (2020).
9	Ries R., eta al, "Improvement of the first flux entry field by laser post-treatment of the thin Nb film on Cu", Supercond. Sci. Technol., accepted for publication (2021).
10	Keckert, S., "Advanced Radio-Frequency Characterization of Thin-Film Superconducting Samples", in Naturwissenschaftlich-Technische Fakultät. Universität Siegen: Siegen, 2019.
11	Kleindienst, R., "Radio Frequency Characterization of Superconductors for Particle Accelerators", in Naturwissenschaftlich-Technische Fakultät., Universität Siegen, 2017.
12	More than other 10 papers will be published in scientific journals and the IPAC'21 and SRF-2021 conference proceedings.

6.2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

WP3	
Type	Author, Title, References, Date
Conference presentation	T. Torims, G. Pikurs, K. Kravalis, A. Ruse, Riga Technical University, Latvia A.G. Chmielewski, A. Pawelec, Z. Zimek, Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology, Poland; G. Mattausch, Fraunhofer Institute for Organic Electronics, Electron Beam and Plasma Technology FEP, Germany M. Vretenar, CERN, Switzerland "Development of a Hybrid Electron Accelerator System for the Treatment of Marine Diesel Exhaust Gases", IPAC-20, 11-th International Particle Accelerator Conference" Proceedings of IPAC2020, Caen, France THVIR14
Conference presentation	T.Smoliński et al. „Ballast water treatment technology for floating “green dock”, NUTECH 2020, Warsaw, 4-7 October 2020, Book of abstracts
Conference presentation	A. Pawelec et al., “Plasma technology to remove NO _x from off-gases”, NUTECH 2020, Warsaw, 4-7 October 2020, Book of abstracts
Conference presentation	Yongxia Sun et al, “Organic pollutant removal from marine diesel engine off-gases under electron beam (EB) and EB hybrid wet scrubber process” NUTECH 2020, Warsaw, 4-7 October 2020, Book of abstracts
Conference presentation	A. Chmielewski et al.,” New trends in electron beam environmental applications”, NUTECH 2020, Warsaw , 4-7 October 2020, Book of abstracts
Conference session	Special session (6 lectures, 3 posters) dedicated to the ARIES project at The International Conference on Development and Applications of Nuclear Technologies NUTECH-2020, 4 – 7 October 2020, Warsaw

Award	International Warsaw Invention Show IWIS 2020, Silver medal for the invention “Method for simultaneous removal of acid inorganic impurities and volatile organic impurities from a stream of waste gases, preferably from the diesel engine and method for removal of impurities”
workshop	VHEE 2020 International Workshop, virtual, 5-7 October 2020, [https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/]
WP4	
Type	<i>Author, Title, References, Date</i>
presentation	M.Seidel et al, Energy Efficiency of Accelerators in the European Programs Eucard2 and ARIES , 11.11.2017, ESSRI 2027, Magurele/Ro
presentation	C.Marchand, Development of Efficient Klystrons , 11.11.2017, ESSRI 2017, Magurele/Ro
CERN report	S. Papadopoulos, S. Ramberger, Magnetic measurements of the vacuum vessel for the High-Gradient four cavity cryomodule (2018)
PSI report	R. M. Bergmann, Liquid Deuterium Cold Source Energy Deposition, PSI – Villigen (2018).
presentation	P.Hamel, High Efficiency Klystron Development at CEA , Uppsala (2019)
presentation	A.Ivanov et al, The impact of magnetic flux trapping on SRF efficiency , Budapest (2019)
presentation	F. Gerigk, Low-loss superconducting cavities, ESSRI 2019, PSI (2019)
presentation	A. Ivanov, Flux expulsion measurement with a flux lens, TTC 2020, 4-7 Feb. 2020, CERN
WP6	
Newsletter	T. Pieloni, M. Zanetti, F. Zimmermann, <i>ACN2020 – Applications of Crystals and Nanotubes</i> , ICFA Beam Dynamics Newsletter no. 79 (2020), JINST 15 T07005
Presentation Symposium	F. Zimmermann, <i>Overview of Future Colliders</i> , Annual and Virtual NSF CBB Colloquium, 23 July 2020
Presentation Symposium	F. Zimmermann, <i>Future Colliders</i> , OWLE Colloquium (worldwide virtual), 3 November 2020
Presentation Workshop	M. Migliorati, <i>Collective effects in FCC-ee</i> , 8th Low Emittance Rings Workshop, 26-30 October 2020 INFN-LNF
Newsletter	G. Franchetti and F. Zimmermann, <i>Mitigation Approaches for Hadron Storage Rings and Synchrotrons (June 22–24 and June 29–July 1, 2020)</i> , ICFA Beam Dynamics Newsletter no. 81 (2021), JINST 16 T03008

Newsletter	G. Franchetti, M. Zanetti, F. Zimmermann, <i>ARIES Workshop on Storage Rings and Gravitational Waves (SRGW2021, February 2–March 11, 2021)</i> , ICFA Beam Dynamics Newsletter no. 81 (2021), JINST 16 T03008
Presentation	F. Zimmermann, <i>Accelerator physics and technology challenges for the XXIst century</i> , IN2P3 Scientific Council, 9 February 2021
Newsletter	<u>R.T. D’Agnolo, <i>Colliding Particles meet Gravitational Waves</i>, CERN EP Newsletter 15 March 2021</u>
Newsletter	G. Franchetti, M. Zanetti, F. Zimmermann, <i>Accelerators probing Gravitational Waves</i> , (APEC 6.6), Accelerating News, no. 36
Newsletter	<u>R. D’Agnolo, G. Franchetti, F. Zimmermann, <i>Accelerators Meet Gravitational Waves</i>, CERN Courier, 25 May 2021</u>
WP14	
Type	<i>Author, Title, References, Date</i>
presentation	M.Losasso, report from WP14; April 21 st 2021
Final PoC project report	T. Proslie, Atomic Layer Deposition: innovative approach for next generation particle accelerators; April 21 st 2021
Final PoC project report	C. P. Welsch, Accelerator Diagnostics using innovative Adaptive Optics (InnoAdo); April 21 st 2021
Final PoC project report	T. TORIMS, Development of hybrid electron accelerator system for the treatment of marine diesel exhaust gases; April 21 st 2021
Final PoC project report	E. Neubauer, Investigation of new methods for the manufacturing of Cu-C composites with tailored thermo-physical properties; April 21 st 2021
Outreach	<u>L. Rossi » Le grand collisionneur LHC du CERN : Les nouvelles technologies pour la découverte de l’infiniment petit » Assemblée Générale Ordinaire IESF – celebration Ampère 2020 - Paris , 17/09/2020</u>
WP15	
Presentations	S. B. Leith. “Investigation of NbN thin films for use in SRF applications” – CERN group meetings, 12/11/2020 and 26/11/2020
Presentations	S. B. Leith. “Progress with SC thin film deposition” - group updates, 04/06/2019, 10/12/2019 and 25/2/2020
Invited talk at TTC 2020	O. Kugeler. “ARIES work package 15 - Thin films SRF”, TTC workshop, CERN, 2020
Invited talk at TTC 2020	S. Keckert. “Overview multilayers – SRF results”, TTC workshop, CERN, 2020
Talk at TTC 2020	D. Turner. “Local magnetometry”, TTC workshop, CERN, 2020

Talks at 9 th International Workshop on Thin Film and New Ideas for pushing the Limits of RF Superconductivity, 15-18 March 2021	O.B. Malyshev. “Main highlights ARIES WP15 team collaboration on Thin Film for Superconducting RF (TF-SRF)”, 2021
	F. Walk. “Bipolar HiPIMS: Correlating plasma parameters to thin film properties”, 2021
	C. Pira. “Nb ₃ Sn films via liquid tin diffusion for SRF application”, 2021
	F. Lockwood Estrin. “Using HiPIMS for V3Si Superconducting Thin Films Nearly all”, 2021
	R. Valizadeh. “Synthesis of Alternative Superconducting Film to Nb for SRF Cavity”, 2021
	S. Leith. “The Development of HiPIMS Multilayer SIS film coatings on Copper for SRF Applications”, 2021
	Ö. Sezgin. “NbN Thin Film-Based Multilayer (S-(I)-S) Structures for SRF Cavities”, 2021
	A. Medvids, “Improvement of Mechanical and Magnetic Properties of Nb/Cu Structure by Laser Radiation for SRF Applications”, 2021
	D. Turner. “DC magnetic field penetration results for Nb thin films with superconducting radiofrequency applications”, 2021
	D. Tikhonov. “Investigation of SIS multilayer films at HZB”, 2021
D. Seal. “A low power test facility for SRF thin film testing with high sample throughput rate”, 2021	
Talks at SRF-21	10 abstracts submitted for reporting at the Virtual 2021 SRF International Conference on RF superconductivity (SRF-21), to be held on 28 th June – 2 nd July 2021.

Meetings of the WPs

<i>Dates</i>	<i>Type of meeting + link</i>	<i>Venue</i>
WP3		
4-7 October 2020	ARIES WP3 session at NUTECH2020 NUTECH2020-conference-abstracts-and-programme.pdf	Warsaw. Poland Hybrid event

WP4		
April 26, 2021	Workshop on Energy Efficient Beam Transport Technologies https://indico.gsi.de/event/11642/	GSI, Darmstadt, Germany
WP6		
22.05. – 01.07.2020	Mitigation Approaches for Hadron Storage Rings and Synchrotrons (Mitigations2020); https://indico.gsi.de/event/10458	Safe virtual space
02.02.-18.03.2021	ARIES Workshop on Storage Rings and Gravitational Waves (SRGW2021), https://indico.cern.ch/event/982987/	Safe virtual space
WP14		
25.06.2021	Reliability, Availability, Maintainability, Inspectability (RAMI) workshop https://indico.cern.ch/event/1048728/	Video

7. Summary of Transnational Access activities at M48

7.1 WP9 MAGNET TESTING

MagNet	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	4	4	22	944
Period 2 (M19-M36)	0	0	3	200
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL				1,144
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	4		30	1,300
Target M49-M56				156

Gersemi	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	0	0	0	0
Period 2 (M19-M36)	0	0	0	0
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL				0
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	3		15	1800
Target M49-M56				1800

7.2 WP10 MATERIAL TESTING

HiRadMat	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	6	6	38	1328
Period 2 (M19-M36)	1	1*	0**	328
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL				1656
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	7		39	664
Target M49-M56				0

UNILAC	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	2	2	21	104
Period 2 (M19-M36)	2	2	12	408
Period 3 (M37-M48)	8		tbc	264
TOTAL				776
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	6		50	768
Target M49-M56				0

7.3 WP11 ELECTRON & PROTON BEAM TESTING

ANKA	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	3	3	6	180
Period 2 (M19-M36)	2	2	8	1688
Period 3 (M37-M48)	2		11	1688
TOTAL	7		25	3556
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	7		22	900
Target M49-M56				0

FLUTE	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	2	2	9	76
Period 2 (M19-M36)	0	0*	0**	80
Period 3 (M37-M48)	8		tbd	80
TOTAL				236
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	3		11	308
Target M49-M56				72

IPHI	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		

Period 1 (M1-M18)	1	1	8	72
Period 2 (M19-M36)	1	1	5	0
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL	2		13	72
Updated targets (Amendment 2)				72

SINBAD	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	0	0	0	0
Period 2 (M19-M36)	0	0	0	0
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL				
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	3		12	210
Target M49-M56				210

VELA	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	1	1	0	0
Period 2 (M19-M36)	1	1	11	80
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL				80
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	5		25	288
Target M49-M56				208

7.4 WP12 RADIO FREQUENCY TESTING

HNOSS	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	2	2	18	1330
Period 2 (M19-M36)	2	2*	24	2084
Period 3 (M37-M48)	1		7	1080
TOTAL			49	4494
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	4		44	3790
Target M49-M56				0

XBox	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	2	2	13	1680
Period 2 (M19-M36)	2	2	11	4000
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL				5680
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	4		24	7500
Target M49-M56				1820

7.5 WP13 PLASMA BEAM TESTING

APOLLON	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	0	0	0	0
Period 2 (M19-M36)	0	0	0	0
Period 3 (M1-M48)	0		0	0
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	1		3	0

LPA-UHI100	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	1	1	4+1 remote	152
Period 2 (M19-M36)	1	1	6	176
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL	2		11	328
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	3		16	488
Target M49-M56				160

LULAL	User-projects		Total no. of users benefitting from the TA	Units of access (1 hour)
	Eligible submissions	Selected		
Period 1 (M1-M18)	1	1	0	0
Period 2 (M19-M36)	2	2	20	517
Period 3 (M37-M48)	0		0	0
TOTAL				517
Updated targets (Amendment 2)	5		30	768
Target M49-M56				251

7.6 TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS SUMMARY

At M48, one year before the end of all TA activities, the 14 ARIES TA facilities have provided in total 18,539 access units to users, out of a total foreseen for the project of 18,856. Even if the overall engagement has been almost achieved (98.3% of total access units provided at one year from the end of the project), the distribution of units among the facilities is very uneven, with some facilities having provided no access yet because of persisting technical problems, and others having provided less access than expected primarily because of the impact of the Covid pandemic that has limited the travel of users to the facilities.

The remaining part of Period 3 (M49-M56) is expected to balance part of the disparities between facilities and to allow globally exceeding the minimum quantity of access to be provided by ARIES.